

APOE from astrocytes restores Alzheimer's A β -pathology and DAM-like responses in APOE deficient microglia

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ABSTRACT

The major genetic risk factor for Alzheimer's disease (AD), *APOE4*, accelerates beta-amyloid (A β) plaque formation, but whether this is caused by APOE expressed in microglia or astrocytes is debated. We express here the human APOE isoforms in astrocytes in an *ApoE*-deficient AD mouse model. This is not only sufficient to restore the amyloid plaque pathology but also induces the characteristic transcriptional pathological responses in *ApoE*-deficient microglia surrounding the plaques. We find that both APOE4 and the protective APOE2 from astrocytes increase fibrillar plaque deposition, but differentially affect soluble A β aggregates. Microglia and astrocytes show specific alterations in function of APOE genotype expressed in astrocytes. Our experiments indicate a central role of the astrocytes in APOE mediated amyloid plaque pathology and in the induction of associated microglia responses.

Keywords: Alzheimer's disease/Astrocytes/Microglia/APOE/ β -amyloid pathology

INTRODUCTION

The *APOE4* variant of apolipoprotein E was identified 30 years ago as the major genetic risk factor for Alzheimer's Disease (AD) at the population level (Corder *et al.*, 1993; Strittmatter *et al.*, 1993; Bennett *et al.*, 2009) while the *APOE2* variant was the first identified protective allele against AD (Corder *et al.*, 1994; Nagy *et al.*, 1995). Apolipoprotein E is a lipid carrier and as such involved directly or indirectly in a spectrum of pathophysiological processes. In AD, its specific role in promoting β -amyloid (A β) plaque pathology is, however, well established (Schmechel *et al.*, 1993; Kok *et al.*, 2009; Fleisher *et al.*, 2013; Murphy *et al.*, 2013). While effects on clearance of A β (Deane *et al.*, 2008; Castellano *et al.*, 2011; Verghese *et al.*, 2013) have been described, the major role is direct promotion of A β fibrillization (Ma *et al.*, 1994; Wisniewski *et al.*, 1994; Castano *et al.*, 1995) as also supported by *in vivo* experiments (Huynh *et al.*, 2017; Liu, Zhao, *et al.*, 2017). This interpretation is supported by genetic studies in humans. The *APOE4* allele is associated with increased amyloid deposition (Polvikoski *et al.*, 1995; Bennett *et al.*, 2009; Hanson *et al.*, 2013; Gonneaud *et al.*, 2016), possibly explaining the early onset of disease in homozygous *APOE4* carriers (Blacker *et al.*, 1997; Martins *et al.*, 2005; Sando *et al.*, 2008; Powell *et al.*, 2021). On the other hand, AD mouse models show limited amyloid plaque pathology in the absence of *ApoE* (Bales *et al.*, 1999; Holtzman, Fagan, *et al.*, 2000; Ulrich *et al.*, 2018). APOE4-targeted replacement mice, expressing the human *APOE4* allele instead of the mouse *ApoE*, crossed with different AD mouse models such as PDAPP, APP/ PS1 Δ E9 and 5xFAD, accelerated plaque formation compared to APOE3-targeted replacement mice (Holtzman, Bales, *et al.*, 2000; Fagan *et al.*, 2002; Bales *et al.*, 2009; Castellano *et al.*, 2011; Youmans *et al.*, 2012; Rodriguez *et al.*, 2014). This has also been observed with viral-vector mediated over-expression of APOE4 isoforms in AD mouse brains (Dodart *et al.*, 2005; Hudry *et al.*, 2013; Zhao *et al.*, 2016).

Logically, it is assumed that the protective effect of *APOE2* is the opposite of *APOE4*. The protective effect is reflected in a low prevalence of *APOE2* alleles in AD patient cohorts (Talbot *et al.*, 1994; West, William Rebeck and Hyman, 1994; Reiman *et al.*, 2020) and reduction of A β plaque load in *APOE2* carriers (Nagy *et al.*, 1995; Polvikoski *et al.*, 1995; Chiang *et al.*, 2010; Kantarci *et al.*, 2012; Serrano-Pozo *et al.*, 2015; Grothe *et al.*, 2017). Other studies suggest that APOE2 protection may be at the level of tau pathology or even at the level of delay in cognitive deficits, without reduction in A β plaque formation (Berlau *et al.*, 2007, 2009). Similarly, in mouse models, the effect of APOE2 on A β plaques remains controversial with some studies confirming decreased amyloid deposition compared to APOE3 (Fagan *et al.*, 2002; Castellano *et al.*, 2011; Hudry *et al.*, 2013; Zhao *et al.*, 2016), while others show similar or even increased deposits (Dodart *et al.*, 2005; Bales *et al.*, 2009; Youmans *et al.*, 2012; Rodriguez *et al.*, 2014). Besides, in many studies the APOE2 genotype was not included when reporting APOE4 isoform-specific effects on amyloid plaque formation (Fryer *et al.*, 2005; Kim *et al.*, 2011; Bien-Ly *et al.*, 2012; Liu, Zhao, *et al.*, 2017; Mahan *et al.*, 2022).

The cellular source that produces the pathologically relevant APOE is another point of debate. The protein is expressed mainly in the liver. However, APOE is not transferred over the blood brain barrier (Lane-Donovan *et al.*, 2016; Huynh *et al.*, 2019) suggesting that astrocytes are the main contributor of APOE in the brain (Boyles *et al.*, 1985; Zhang *et al.*, 2014). Under stress conditions APOE might be expressed by neurons (Xu *et al.*, 2006), and under these conditions APOE4 impairs synaptic function and aggravates tau pathology (Andrews-Zwilling *et al.*, 2010; Buttini *et al.*, 2010; Knoferle *et al.*, 2014; Koutsodendrakis *et al.*, 2023). Neuronal APOE, however, does not seem to be associated specifically with amyloid pathology. In contrast, microglia can significantly upregulate APOE expression as part of their DAM (Disease Associated Microglia) response to the amyloid plaques (Keren-Shaul *et al.*, 2017; Krasemann *et al.*, 2017; Sala Frigerio *et al.*, 2019; Chen *et al.*, 2020). However, reconstitution of APOE expression in microglia only in an *ApoE* knockout background (Mancuso *et al.*, 2024) or microglia-specific knockout of *APOE* had no effect on amyloid plaque formation or microglial association with plaques (Henningfield *et al.*, 2022). This suggests that APOE upregulation in microglia, while an important characteristic of DAM cell state induction, is not directly involved in the initial plaque deposition, which as we discussed, seems to be the main AD causing pathological effect of APOE4.

Thus, it appears that in the very early phases of AD, when A β is believed to seed small soluble aggregates, and no DAM cell state is yet induced in the microglia, astrocytes serve as the main source of APOE in the brain. APOE expression specifically under the GFAP-promoter modified plaque deposition in an isoform-specific manner (Holtzman, Bales, *et al.*, 2000; Fagan *et al.*, 2002; Liu, Zhao, *et al.*, 2017), while astrocyte specific knockout of *APOE3/APOE4* led to reduction of A β plaque formation (Mahan *et al.*, 2022), in line with this hypothesis. Therefore, we investigated whether it is indeed sufficient to express APOE in astrocytes to induce A β plaque formation, and more importantly, whether that is sufficient to induce the DAM microglia response. Interestingly, in our experimental paradigm, APOE2 expression only in astrocytes did not reduce the amyloid plaque formation compared to APOE3, even when APOE4 had significantly higher levels than both. We present transcriptomic changes in astrocytes expressing the different APOE isoforms, that suggest possible impairment of proteostasis and autophagy in APOE4 astrocytes. We provide evidence that microglia lacking endogenous APOE expression, can be stirred in their response to amyloid pathology by APOE secreted by astrocytes. Moreover, we show that the APOE effect of astrocytes on amyloid plaques is largely cell autonomous, as in the absence of microglia, amyloid plaques are still generated.

RESULTS

Expression of APOE in astrocytes is sufficient to restore fibrillar amyloid plaque pathology

In order to study the role of astrocyte-derived APOE on amyloid plaque pathology, we expressed the different human APOE isoforms (further referred to as APOE2, APOE3 and APOE4), along with reporter mCherry protein, specifically in astrocytes in an *ApoE*-deficient AD mouse model (*App*^{NL-G-F} x *ApoE*^{-/-}), using recombinant AAV2/8 particles (injected ICV at postnatal day 2/3, see Materials and Methods for details) and the astrocyte specific promoter ALDH1L1 (Fig. 1A). AAV particles expressing only mCherry protein were used as controls (further referred to as APOEKO). At 2 months of age, we observed mCherry expression in the cortical regions, along with limited spread in the subcortical area (Fig. S1A). At 6 months of age, we used immunofluorescence to confirm mCherry expression in ALDH1L1+ astrocytes (Fig. S1B). The ALDH1L1 promoter is specifically expressed in astrocytes in mouse brain (Cahoy *et al.*, 2008; Zhang *et al.*, 2014) and has been extensively used to target gene expression in an astrocyte-specific setting (Clarke *et al.*, 2018; Michalovicz *et al.*, 2019; Hasel *et al.*, 2021; Endo *et al.*, 2022; Mahan *et al.*, 2022). Using flow cytometry, we found that around 14% of ACSA2+ astrocytes expressed mCherry (Fig. S1Cii) and around 90% of the mCherry-positive cells were positive for astrocyte marker ACSA2 (Fig. S1Ciii). It is likely that remaining mCherry-positive cells are a subpopulation of astrocytes that are ACSA2-negative. We do not exclude that a small number of non-astrocytic cells are transduced by the viral particles. However, we confirmed by immunofluorescence the lack of mCherry expression in NeuN+ neurons, Apc+ oligodendrocytes and Iba1+ microglia (Fig.

S1D). We also confirmed APOE expression in mCherry+ cells (Fig. S1E), demonstrating that we reconstituted human APOE expression in astrocytes.

We characterized the amyloid pathology in the transduced mice at 6 months of age. *App*^{NL-G-F} mice exhibited a high load of amyloid plaque deposits in cortical regions as observed by X-34 staining (Fig. S2B). This was largely absent when they were crossed with *ApoE*^{-/-} mice (Figs. 1B, S2A-B). Expression of human APOE isoforms in astrocytes restored the fibrillar A β plaque depositions in the AAV-transduced cortical regions (Figs. 1B, S2A). APOE4 and, remarkably, also APOE2, showed significantly increased load of fibrillar plaques compared to APOE3 reconstituted animals (Fig. 1C). We further quantified morphological differences, namely size and compactness (Fig. S3A), of individual A β plaques between the groups (see Material and Methods for details). The APOE3 group showed a significant increase in the proportion of medium sized plaques in the range of 20-40 μ m diameter, while APOE2 and APOE4 both showed increased abundance of larger plaques (above 40 μ m diameter) (Fig. S3B). Plaques in the APOE3 group showed significantly increased compactness across all size ranges (Fig. S3C-i-iii). Therefore, fibrillar plaques formed in the presence of APOE3 tend to be smaller and more compact morphologically compared to plaques formed in the presence of APOE2 and APOE4.

We quantified human APOE expression in homogenized brain tissues using a human APOE specific ELISA (Fig. 1D) and qPCR (Fig. S1F) and found no significant overall differences in levels of expression between APOE2, APOE3 and APOE4 groups (Figs. 1D, S1F). Interestingly, we observed that APOE secreted from astrocytes colocalized with X-34 positive fibrillar amyloid plaques (Fig. S2C). Therefore, we wondered whether each APOE isoform could differentially affect plaque formation within each experimental group. We used ELISA to quantify the plaque associated guanidine soluble A β ₄₂ levels in the different samples as a quantitative read out for amyloid deposition. Linear regression analysis to examine the relationship between APOE levels and guanidine soluble A β ₄₂ levels (Fig. 1E), showed a relatively strong positive association between APOE4 and A β ₄₂ ($R^2 = 0.61$, slope = 0.23, $p = 0.007$). APOE2 follows a similar trend ($R^2 = 0.43$, slope = 0.11, $p = 0.077$), while APOE3 levels showed no association ($R^2 = 0.006$, slope = 0.005, $p = 0.843$). Thus, APOE4 has a strong dose-dependent effect on amyloid fibrillization in this model of plaque deposition.

We wondered whether the absence of fibrillar amyloid plaques in the APOEKO group led to an increase in soluble A β species in the mouse brains. Using the single molecule pulldown (SiMPull) technique (Sideris *et al.*, 2021), we quantified the number of soluble A β aggregates (Figs. 1F-G) eluted by soaking the brain tissue in artificial CSF. APOEKO mouse brains showed a significant increase in the number of soluble A β aggregates compared to other experimental groups (Fig. 1G), confirming a shift towards soluble species in the brain parenchyma in the absence of plaque deposition. Interestingly, the APOE4 group which showed a high level of fibrillar plaque deposition, showed low levels of soluble A β aggregates (Fig. 1G). APOE2 was intermediary between APOEKO and APOE4. Most remarkably, APOE3, which showed lower amounts of fibrillar plaque accumulation than APOE4 (Fig. 1C), displayed low levels of soluble aggregates similar to APOE4 in this assay (Fig. 1G).

Overall, our data confirm and extend the notion that APOE secreted from astrocytes is central in the formation of amyloid plaques in mice. While APOE4 accelerates this process, APOE2 also shows a similar trend, especially when compared to APOE3, indicating that the APOE2 protective effect is not simply the opposite of APOE4's accelerating effect on plaque formation in AD, at least in the AD mouse model used here.

APOE expression modulates astrocyte cell-states in *App*^{NL-G-F} mouse brain

Our data points to an important role for astrocytes in amyloid plaque formation and a distinct role of the different APOE isoforms in this process at 6 months of age. There are only limited transcriptomic studies available that investigate the effect of the human *APOE* variants on astrocyte phenotypes *in vivo* (Serrano-Pozo *et al.*, 2021; Tcw *et al.*, 2022; Lee *et al.*, 2023). We therefore decided to analyze the transcriptome profiles of mCherry+/ACSA2+ astrocytes from mouse brains at 6 months of age using

droplet-based scRNAseq. After filtering out non-astrocyte cells and low-quality cells, we retained 18,667 astrocytes across the 4 experimental groups. Clustering analysis revealed 12 astrocyte subpopulations (Fig. 2A) with unique gene signatures (Fig. 2B, Table S1-S2), agreeing with the high level of regional and functional heterogeneity of this cell type in the brain. The clusters divided broadly into two groups based on telencephalon and non-telencephalon identity, as previously described (Zeisel *et al.*, 2018) (Figs. 2A, B). Clusters a1, a3 and a4 show a high expression of *Agt*, *Itih3* and *Slc6a11* which are markers for non-telencephalon astrocytes. Clusters a0, a2, a5, a6, a7, a8 and a9 show increased expression of *Mfge8*, *Lhx2* and *Ppp1r3g* which are markers for telencephalon astrocytes (Fig. S4A). Since we observed changes in plaque pathology according to APOE isoforms in the cortical areas, we focused on only the telencephalon astrocytes for further analysis. Out of these, Cluster a2 was enriched for homeostatic genes of cortical astrocytes such as *Epha5*, *Id3*, *Car2* (Murai and Pasquale, 2011; Batiuk *et al.*, 2020; Theparambil *et al.*, 2020). Subventricular zone astrocytes were enriched in Cluster a5 (*Slc38a1*, *Hopx*, *Zic1* and *Zic4*) (Mizrak *et al.*, 2019; Hasel *et al.*, 2021), hippocampal astrocytes in Cluster a7 (*Hopx*, *Hes5* and *Nr2f1*) (Hatakeyama *et al.*, 2004; Li *et al.*, 2015; Zweifel *et al.*, 2018; Bertacchi *et al.*, 2020) and Cluster a9 (*Hopx*, *Gfap* and *Igfbp5*) (Ye and D'Ercole, 1998; Bushong *et al.*, 2002; Li *et al.*, 2015), and striatal astrocytes in Cluster a8 (*Crym*) (Chai *et al.*, 2017; Ollivier *et al.*, 2024). We also identified two reactive populations of astrocytes. Cluster a10 was mainly characterized by downregulation of homeostatic astrocyte genes such as *Slc1a2*, *Glul*, *Aqp4*, and *Gja1* (Fig. S4B), and upregulated *Gfap*, *Vim*, *S100a6* and *Meg3* (Figs. 2B, S4B). Cluster a10 showed, in addition, increased expression of plaque induced genes (PIGs) such as *Cyba*, *Gpx4*, *Igfbp5*, *S100a6*, *Cd9*, and *Gfap*, previously proposed to be part of the combined microglia-astrocyte response to amyloid plaques (Chen *et al.*, 2020) (Fig. S4C). Besides, Cluster a11 is characterized by upregulation of interferon genes such as *Cxcl10*, *Ifit3*, *ligp1* and *Ifitm3*, indicating a cell-state of astrocyte associated to inflammation (Hasel *et al.*, 2021) (Fig. S4D).

Thus, our APOE reconstitution experiment covered a wide range of different astrocyte subtypes and cell states. Overall, different APOE isoforms do not seem to have a major effect on the clusters apart from the APOEKO condition where Cluster a0 was strongly enriched and Cluster a6 completely absent (Fig. 2C). Functional enrichment (Gene Ontology: Biological Process database) analysis of Cluster a6 showed enrichment for terms related to negative regulation of cellular (GO:0048523) and biological (GO:0048519) processes (Fig. 2D), driven by genes such as *Pde10a*, *Emd*, *Nr4a2*, and *Eprs* (Table S2). Among the top markers of Cluster a6 are genes involved in inflammatory pathways (*Fos*, *Junb*, *Nr4a2*) (Zenz *et al.*, 2008; Estrada *et al.*, 2020) and cell proliferation and communication (*Btg2*, *Ccn1*) (Jun and Lau, 2011; Yuniati *et al.*, 2019; Suzuki *et al.*, 2021) (Fig. 2B, Table S1). Cluster a0 showed enrichment for terms related to sterol (GO:0016126) and cholesterol (GO:0006695) biosynthetic processes (Fig. 2D), driven by genes such as *Msmo1*, *Insig1* and *Hmgcr* (Table S2). To explore the effect of APOE deficiency on astrocyte transcriptomes further, we performed differential gene expression analysis to compare each experimental group against the APOE3 group (Fig. 3A, Table S3). We found that the highest number of DEGs were in the APOEKO group- 375 UP and 321 DOWN genes, compared to number of DEGs in APOE2 ($p = 4.4e-64$) or APOE4 ($p = 4e-85$). Top upregulated genes in the APOEKO astrocytes such as *Ubb*, *Ubc* and *Ctsl* (Fig. 3B, Table S3), are involved in protein degradation, while *Ptgds* (Kanekiyo *et al.*, 2007; Kannaian *et al.*, 2019) and *Cst3* (Sastre *et al.*, 2004; Mi *et al.*, 2007), are associated with inhibition of A β fibrillization, in line with absence of amyloid plaques in APOEKO mice. Other upregulated genes such as *Ndr2* (Feng *et al.*, 2022; Zhang *et al.*, 2023), *Gpx4* (Chen *et al.*, 2020) and *Hmgb1* (Fan *et al.*, 2016) are known modulators of astrocyte reactivity.

We compared next the differential effects of APOE4 vs. APOE3 and APOE2 vs. APOE3 (Fig. 3D). Compared to APOE3, both APOE4 and APOE2 significantly upregulated *Pde10a*, which was also highly upregulated in Cluster a6 (Fig. 2B) and showed minimal expression in APOEKO astrocytes (Fig. 3B, C). *Pde10a* belongs to a family of phosphodiesterases and their inhibition has been suggested to modulate AD and other neurodegenerative disorders, potentially activating CREB (cAMP response element-binding)- dependent synaptic plasticity and memory formation (O'Connor *et al.*, 2004; Puzzo *et al.*,

2009; García-Osta *et al.*, 2012), but these effects were related to expression of *Pde10a* in neurons, not astrocytes. Both APOE4 and APOE2 astrocytes also upregulated reactive markers such as *Neat1* and *Cd9* (Chen *et al.*, 2020; Habib *et al.*, 2020; Irwin *et al.*, 2023). APOE4 astrocytes specifically upregulated several mitochondrial genes (*mt-Nd1*, *mt-Cytb*, *mt-Rnr2*). Notably, APOE4 also downregulated several genes involved in autophagy (*Actg1*, *Tax1bp1*, *Sqstm1*, *Lamp1*, *Lamp2*) (Fig. 3D) and lipid metabolism (*Msmo1*, *Hmgcs1*). On the other hand, APOE2 astrocytes, similar to APOEKO, upregulated genes involved in protein degradation such as *Ubb* and *Uba52*, with downregulation of lipid metabolism related genes (*Etnppl*, *Insig1*) (Fig. 3D). Both APOE4 and APOE2 differ from APOE3 in the sense that APOE3 is characterized by upregulated interferon response genes such as *Irf27*, *Lgals3bp*, *Ifit3* and *Ifitm3* (Fig. 3D). APOE3 astrocytes also upregulated genes involved in proteostasis (*Hspa8*, *Hsp90ab1*, *Hspa5*), *Sesn3* that reduces reactive oxygen species (ROS) in stress induced state, genes regulating phospholipase enzymes/PI signaling (*Acsl3*, *Pla2g7*, *Plcd4*, *Prex2*), and synaptic plasticity (*Nnat*). Thus, different APOE isoforms induce different transcriptomic responses in astrocytes in the *App*^{NL-G-F} mouse model, with potential impairment of proteostasis and autophagy in APOE4-expressing astrocytes.

We also explored the astrocyte transcriptome for expression level and possible dysregulation of previously identified AD risk genes (Bellenguez *et al.*, 2022) (Fig. S4E). Overall, astrocytes expressed only a small number of these risk genes. Out of these, *Clu* and *Cox7c* become highly upregulated in the absence of APOE, while *Abca1* and *Sort1* get downregulated (Figs. 3B, S4E). *Clu* has been reported to have the opposite effect of *ApoE* on amyloid pathology, with overexpression of *Clu* in AD mice showing decreased plaque deposition (Chen *et al.*, 2021). Notably, we saw decreased expression of *Fermt2* and *Ctsb* in APOE4 astrocytes (Fig. S4E), but the difference was not significant compared to APOE3 group (Table S3). A recent study has shown that downregulation of *Fermt2* in astrocytes can lead to reduction of territory size and associated cognitive deficits (Endo *et al.*, 2022). This suggests that APOE expression in an amyloid environment is linked to the modulation of AD risk genes in astrocytes.

Overall, our analysis indicates that absence or expression of APOE has profound effects on astrocyte transcriptional features, indicating the multifunctionality of the protein. The differences between APOE2, APOE3 and APOE4 are less outspoken, but cover important functions such as interferon response genes, proteostasis genes, PI signaling, lipid metabolism, and as salient observation the upregulation of *Pde10a*.

Fibrillar plaques induced by astrocyte-derived APOE elicit a reactive response in *ApoE*-deficient microglia

Reactive microglia states associated to amyloid plaques strongly upregulate *ApoE* expression (Keren-Shaul *et al.*, 2017; Krasemann *et al.*, 2017; Sala Frigerio *et al.*, 2019). We therefore questioned whether APOE from astrocytes is necessary and sufficient to restore the response of *ApoE*-deficient microglia to amyloid plaques in our model.

We used immunofluorescence to analyze the morphological changes in microglia near the astrocyte-induced amyloid plaques. We indeed observed increased microglial clustering around the fibrillar plaque deposits (Fig. 4A). To confirm this, we segmented individual microglia (Figs. S5A-B) and classified them based on their proximity to amyloid plaques as “plaque-associated” (within X34+ thresholded plaque area and up to 5 μ m outside a plaque’s edge) or “non-plaque-associated” (Figs. S5C, D). Plaque-associated microglia clustered together with a significantly lower distance to neighbouring microglia, compared to the well-tiled microglia present away from plaques (Fig. S5E). Plaque-associated microglia also had significantly lower territory size (convex area) (Fig. S5Fi) and total process length (Fig. S5Fii), indicating a less branched, amoeboid morphology, characteristic of reactive microglia. We confirmed that plaque-associated microglia stained positive for phagocytic marker Cd68 (Fig. 4B, S5G) and lysosomal protease *Ctsd* (Fig. 4C, S5H), characteristic of the DAM cell state (Keren-Shaul *et al.*, 2017). Thus, *ApoE*-deficient microglia are still able to adopt a reactive state in response to fibrillar plaques induced by astrocyte-derived APOE.

Next, we wondered whether the APOE isoforms influence microglial responses, in terms of number and morphological changes. We observed a significantly higher number of microglia in the AAV-transduced region for APOE4 compared to other groups (Fig. 4Di), but regression analysis demonstrated this was due to the strong positive association ($R^2 = 0.86$, slope = 731.09, $p = 3.7e-12$) of total microglia numbers with the level of plaque load, independent of APOE isoform (Fig. 4Dii). Interestingly, this increase in microglia population with plaque load was driven by increased number of plaque-associated microglia ($R^2 = 0.97$, slope = 973.13, $p = 2e-16$) while the non-plaque-associated population remained relatively stable despite increase in plaque load ($R^2 = 0.5$, slope = -242.04, $p = 3.5e-05$) (Fig. 4Dii). Additionally, there were no significant changes in microglial morphology (territory size and total process length), for either non-plaque-associated (Fig. S5I) or plaque-associated microglia (Fig. S5J), between the different experimental groups. Therefore, at morphological level, microglial responses to fibrillar plaques do not seem to depend on the isoform of APOE produced by astrocytes but are likely mediated directly by the plaque load.

In order to explore the changes in microglial reactivity at the transcriptomic level, we performed droplet-based scRNAseq on CD11b+/CD45-low microglia isolated at 6 months of age from the mouse brains expressing different APOE isoforms in astrocytes. After filtering out non-microglial cells and low-quality cells, we retained 18,569 *ApoE*-deficient microglia over the four experimental groups (APOEKO, APOE2, APOE3 and APOE4). Unbiased clustering analysis led to the identification of 7 sub-populations of microglia (Figs. S6A-B, Table S4-S5). We did not find major shifts in cell states as observed in other experimental paradigms ((Keren-Shaul *et al.*, 2017; Sala Frigerio *et al.*, 2019) probably because the AAV vector restores amyloid plaque formation only in the area of transduction (Fig. S2A). It is indeed remarkable that the effects of APOE expression in astrocytes on amyloid plaque formation is limited to those brain area where the APOE is expressed, despite APOE being a secreted protein. As we isolated microglia from the whole brain, including the non-transduced regions, only a fraction of the total pool of microglia is exposed to the amyloid plaques. However, we observed interesting shifts in gene signatures by performing differential gene expression analysis (Fig. S7A, Table S6). Among the upregulated genes in the APOEKO group were several genes involved in the cytokine response state (*Ccl3*, *Ccl4*, *Ccl12*, *Il1a*, *Gpr84*, *Jun*) (Fig. S7B). Thus, APOEKO, which shows absence of fibrillar plaques and increased soluble A β aggregates, is associated with microglia tending to adopt a cytokine response state. Interestingly, among the different sets of DEGs, the highest intersection was observed between APOEKO and APOE4 ($p = 4.2e-78$), where 52 genes were commonly upregulated in the two groups (Fig. S7A, S7C, Table S6) including significant overlap ($p = 2.8e-11$) of a small subset of plaque induced genes (PIGs) (*C1qb*, *C1qc*, *Cd63*, *Cd9*, *Cst3*, *Fcer1g*, *Hexb*, *Ly86*) (Chen *et al.*, 2020) (Fig. S7C, Table S6). Their upregulation in the APOEKO group which lack fibrillar plaques, suggests that induction of these plaque-associated microglial markers possibly precedes fibrillar plaque formation in amyloid models. We compared also the differentially expressed genes in APOE4 vs. APOE3 and APOE2 vs. APOE3 to understand the differential effect of the disease promoting and the disease protective allele versus APOE3 that is considered neutral (Fig. S7D). We observed that compared to APOE2, APOE4 had a significant upregulation of several DAM marker genes such as *Cd74*, *Cst7*, *Cd63*, *Cd9*, *Ccl6*, complement cascade genes (*C1qa*, *C1qb*, *C1qc*) and the pro-inflammatory gene *Nfkb1a* (Sousa *et al.*, 2018). This was accompanied by downregulation of homeostatic genes (*Cx3cr1*, *P2ry13*, *Ccr5*, *Siglech*). Also, *Mertk* which is necessary for detection and engulfment of amyloid plaques by microglia (Huang *et al.*, 2021), and *Inpp5d*, a known AD risk factor which has a role in limiting plaque formation (Castranio *et al.*, 2023), are downregulated in APOE4. Interestingly, compared to APOE2 and APOE4, APOE3 upregulated several markers of interferon response in microglia (*Ifitm3*, *Ifit3*, *Ifi2712a*, *Lgals3bp*, *Stat1*) (Figs. S7D). APOE3 also showed an upregulation of antigen presentation genes (*H2-K1*, *H2-D1*, *H2-Q7*).

Overall, our data show that *ApoE*-deficient microglia are able to react to fibrillar plaques mounting a DAM-like response when APOE is provided via astrocytes.

Astrocyte-derived APOE is sufficient for fibrillar amyloid plaque pathology

Our data suggest two possibilities: either APOE from the astrocytes acts directly on amyloid plaque formation and then microglia respond to the plaques formed, or APOE directly modifies microglia responses and thus they sculpt the amyloid plaques with the help of the APOE delivered by the astrocytes.

To address this, we depleted microglia using PLX3397 treatment at 2 months of age before the fibrillar plaques become visible and continued treatment until the mice were 6 months of age (Fig. 5A). Despite strong depletion of microglia (percentage reductions for APOE2: 83%, APOE3: 77%, APOE4: 87%) under those conditions (Figs. 5B, S8A), fibrillar plaque deposition in APOE expressing cortical regions remained substantial, with only APOE4 group showing statistically significant decrease in plaque load upon depletion (Fig. 5C). As depletion of microglia was performed at 2 months and initial amyloid plaque seeding might have occurred already before that time point, we cannot rule out the possibility that microglia played a role in the APOE induced initial seeding of the plaques or that the remaining microglia are sufficient to induce plaque seeds.

Since we have earlier seen that APOE levels also influence A β plaque deposition (Fig. 1E), we used multiple regression analysis to account for the confounding effect of APOE levels while comparing guanidine-soluble A β_{42} levels between PLX3397-treated and untreated animals in each experimental group (Fig. 5D). It is notable that especially in the APOE3 mice, the APOE levels are increased in the microglia depleted brains (Fig. S8Bii). This increase in APOE levels was present in APOE4 mice as well (Fig. S8Biii), with APOE2 mice showing a similar non-significant trend (Fig. S8Bi). Interestingly, for the APOE3 group, like above (Fig. 1E), we found no significant association between A β_{42} levels and APOE levels and there was no significant shift in mean A β_{42} levels ($\beta = -28.53$, SE = 38.31, $p = 0.4708$) with PLX-treatment. On the other hand, both the APOE2 group ($\beta = -148.2$, SE = 32.22, $p = 0.0013$) and the APOE4 group ($\beta = -357.1$, SE = 60.64, $p = 0.0002$) showed a statistically significant decrease in mean A β_{42} levels with PLX-treatment compared to the non-treated group (Fig. 5D). Therefore, this suggests that while APOE from astrocytes is sufficient for plaque deposition at 6 months of age in this model, microglia play a role in modulating A β pathology in APOE2 and APOE4 expressing mice.

DISCUSSION

We investigated the role of APOE in the interplay of astrocytes, microglia and amyloid plaques. The study confirms that APOE derived from astrocytes is sufficient to induce fibrillar A β plaques. It was unexpected that the protective APOE2 isoform had similar, albeit less pronounced, effects as pathogenic APOE4 on amyloid plaque formation in our experiments. Thus, its protective role in AD is likely downstream of the amyloid plaque formation, affecting the cellular phase of the disease, i.e. the response of the cells in the brain to amyloid plaques (De Strooper and Karran, 2016).

Previous studies have shown that knocking out mouse *ApoE* leads to a significant reduction of fibrillar plaque formation in different AD mouse models (Bales *et al.*, 1999; Holtzman, Fagan, *et al.*, 2000; Ulrich *et al.*, 2018). We confirm here in the *App*^{NL-G-F} mouse that despite the presence of strong aggregation promoting mutations in this particular A β sequence, *ApoE* deletion almost annihilates the generation of fibrillar amyloid plaques, while increasing the soluble A β aggregate species (Fig. 1). These species induce a cytokine response (Mancuso *et al.*, 2019) in the *ApoE*-deficient microglia. Interestingly, *ApoE*-deficient astrocytes upregulate genes associated with inhibition of A β fibrillization (*Ptgds* and *Cst3*) and regulation of protein degradation (*Ubb*, *Ubc* and *Ctsl*) (Wegiel *et al.*, 2000; Apelt, Ach and Schliebs, 2003; Liu, Hu, *et al.*, 2017; Davis *et al.*, 2021). Overall, loss of APOE expression has clearly multiple effects on the astrocyte-amyloid plaque-microglia interactions, in accordance with the central role of APOE in this important aspect of AD pathogenesis. It has been reported that reduction of fibrillar amyloid plaques via astrocytic-APOE knockout (Xiong *et al.*, 2023), but not microglial-APOE knockout (Henningfield *et al.*, 2022), results in a shift towards formation of cerebral amyloid angiopathy (CAA). However, we did not investigate the formation of CAA in our model and future studies will be needed to understand this aspect of cell-specific APOE on plaque pathology.

Restoration of APOE expression in astrocytes alone is sufficient to induce formation of fibrillar plaques and microglia reactivity, extending findings from previous studies (Holtzman, Bales, *et al.*, 2000; Liu, Zhao, *et al.*, 2017; Mahan *et al.*, 2022). In general experiments suggest the order of APOE4 > APOE3 > APOE2 for effects on amyloid deposition (Fagan *et al.*, 2002; Castellano *et al.*, 2011; Hudry *et al.*, 2013; Zhao *et al.*, 2016), and therefore our observation that APOE2 is more similar to APOE4 than APOE3 in that regard in our model, is somewhat puzzling. Nevertheless other studies have also reported that APOE2 expression is associated with similar or even higher plaque load than APOE3 (Dodart *et al.*, 2005; Bales *et al.*, 2009; Youmans *et al.*, 2012; Rodriguez *et al.*, 2014). Interestingly, having an APOE2 allele (Berlau *et al.*, 2007, 2009) or the rare isoform APOE3Ch (Christchurch variant) (Arboleda-Velasquez *et al.*, 2019), shields patients against dementia even in the presence of high amyloid plaque load. The protective effects of APOE3Ch downstream of the amyloid plaque formation (on which a relative modest effect was observed) were also seen in an AD amyloid mouse model where overexpression had stronger effect in reducing tau seeding and propagation along with neuronal dystrophy around plaques upon injection of AD-tau brain extract (Chen *et al.*, 2023).

No consensus exists whether and how additional pathophysiological functions of APOE2 and APOE4 contribute to the specific risk of AD. A major problem to clarify the role of APOE in Alzheimer's disease specifically and to define a therapeutic hypothesis to support a translational approach, is the pleiotropic function of APOE. Indeed, APOE4 has been implicated in the proinflammatory state in microglia (Brown *et al.*, 2002; Colton, Brown and Vitek, 2005; Vitek, Brown and Colton, 2009; Lin *et al.*, 2018; Lanfranco *et al.*, 2021; Serrano-Pozo *et al.*, 2021) and astrocytes (Arnaud *et al.*, 2022); endolysosomal dysfunction (Ji *et al.*, 2002; Nuriel *et al.*, 2017; Prasad and Rao, 2018; Xian *et al.*, 2018; Pohlkamp *et al.*, 2021); impaired autophagy (Simonovitch *et al.*, 2016, 2019; Parcon *et al.*, 2018); inducing and promoting spreading of tau pathology, likely mediated by APOE receptors (Brecht *et al.*, 2004; Shi *et al.*, 2017, 2021; Rauch *et al.*, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2021); neurodegeneration (Agosta *et al.*, 2009; Susanto *et al.*, 2015; Lupton *et al.*, 2016); maintaining integrity of pericytes and blood brain barrier (Bell *et al.*, 2012; Montagne *et al.*, 2020, 2021); and impaired myelination in oligodendrocytes (Blanchard *et al.*, 2022). We suggest that the APOE2 protective effect is largely driven by effects on the cellular reactions downstream of the amyloid plaque formation. We cannot exclude however that the APOE2 promoting effect on amyloid plaques as seen in the current work is model specific, and that expressing APOE2 also in other cell types might induce amyloid plaque reducing effects. It has also been shown that APOE2 expression leads to increased APOE levels in mouse models and human brain (Riddell *et al.*, 2008; Bales *et al.*, 2009; Conejero-Goldberg *et al.*, 2014), which can influence amyloid pathology. This is not recapitulated in our model due to inherent limitation of AAV-mediated overexpression.

APOE3 expression in astrocytes in our experiments results in two phenomena: (1) the restoration of amyloid plaque formation at 6 months and (2) the decrease in soluble A β aggregates in these animals. At first glance, increased fibrilization might explain decreased levels of soluble A β aggregates, but the APOE2 allele causes more amyloid plaques than APOE3 in our model, while it also leaves more soluble A β aggregates in the extracellular milieu (Figs. 1C and 1G). In addition, APOE2, but not APOE3, shows a dose dependent relationship between level of expression and amyloid aggregation (Fig. 1E), as APOE4 does. The results thus indicate that the relationship between APOE genotypes and A β plaque formation is not simple. For the interpretation of the data, it is important to take into account that APOE is secreted here only by astrocytes but is taken up via LDL receptors into the endosomal compartments of all cell types in the brain, including the microglia and astrocytes. A β , when endocytosed, becomes concentrated in the acidic endosomal compartments, which promotes amyloid fibril formation and then secretion (Knauer *et al.*, 1992; Chung *et al.*, 1999; Hu *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, uptake of A β bound to APOE might cause increased concentrations of A β in these acidic compartments. Thus, in the absence of APOE, clearance of A β is lowered, resulting in increased soluble A β aggregates in the medium as demonstrated with the APOEKO. When APOE3 is present, A β peptides are taken up by astrocytes and microglia, resulting in a decrease of soluble A β (Figs 1F-G). This process is receptor

mediated and therefore likely saturable, hence there was no concentration dependent effect of APOE3 on uptake of A β in the overexpression condition of our experiment. When a critical concentration of A β is reached in the endosomes, A β fibrilization is induced, leading to the release of A β fibrils and the generation of A β plaques extracellularly as seen in Figs. 1B-C and measured as an increase in guanidine extractable A β_{42} in Fig. 1E. The APOE4 dose-dependent effect on the formation of amyloid plaques is not at the level of uptake, as the effect remains dose dependent at high concentrations. APOE4 affects however the endosomal-lysosomal pathway (Nuriel *et al.*, 2017) and the APOE4 induced recycling block can be rescued by decreasing pH (Xian *et al.*, 2018). These effects on the recycling pathway are, in contrast to the saturable uptake, potentially dose dependent and we speculate that they result in less degradation and more release of fibrillized A β . Less is known about the effect of APOE2 in these mechanisms. From our data it seems that APOE2 is less effective in clearing soluble A β from the extracellular milieu (hence increased soluble A β aggregates compared to APOE3) but because it also increases deposition of amyloid fibrils, APOE2 must have a similar effect as APOE4 on the functioning of endosomes. Kinetic studies should help to understand how precisely different APOE genotypes modulate these different aspects of amyloid plaque biology.

Astrocytes are a highly heterogeneous group of brain cells and future studies need to explore the differential contribution of these subtypes in pathological conditions. In our model, APOE expression with the AAV was induced in different subtypes of astrocytes in the mouse brain (Fig. 2A). We identified cell states (Clusters a0 and a6) which are clearly affected by APOE expression. Enrichment of APOEKO group in Cluster a0, which is marked by processes related to lipid metabolism is expected in the absence of a lipoprotein like APOE. Cluster a6 which is exclusively present in the APOE-expressing groups, and thus also the plaque-bearing brains, is enriched for genes modulating inflammatory pathways which might play a role in astrocyte reactivity towards amyloid pathology. Differential gene expression analysis of APOE2 and APOE4 versus APOE3 showed downregulation of several autophagy-related genes specifically in APOE4 expressing astrocytes, and not in APOE2 astrocytes. This is in line with evidence from brain samples of APOE4 patients showing downregulation of autophagy components (Parcon *et al.*, 2018) and supports the role of astrocyte-mediated autophagy in degradation of A β (Simonovitch *et al.*, 2016, 2019).

Microglia are the main responders to amyloid plaques, mounting a DAM response (disease associated microglial cell-state response) (Keren-Shaul *et al.*, 2017), which also causes the induction of APOE expression in these cells. The DAM response is dependent on APOE expression (Krasemann *et al.*, 2017; Sala Frigerio *et al.*, 2019) but it was thought that APOE expression in microglia was essential. Recent data also suggests a cell autonomous role of microglia-specific APOE4 expression in blocking the DAM response, compared to APOE3 (Liu *et al.*, 2023; Yin, Rosenzweig, *et al.*, 2023). In our model, we have presented non cell autonomous effect of different astrocyte-specific APOE isoforms on microglial response to amyloid pathology. At morphological level, we demonstrated increased microglial clustering (Fig. 4A), and specific staining of DAM markers (Fig. 4B) in *ApoE*^{-/-} microglia surrounding the amyloid plaques. At transcriptional level, microglia from the APOE4 group upregulated several DAM markers (*Cd74*, *Cst7*, *Cd63*, *Cd9*, *Ccl6*), complement cascade genes (*C1qa*, *C1qb*, *C1qc*) and the pro-inflammatory gene *Nfkb1a* (Sousa *et al.*, 2018), similar to transcriptomic changes in microglia from APOE4 AD individuals (Serrano-Pozo *et al.*, 2021). In both astrocytes and microglia, there was an enrichment of interferon response and antigen-presentation genes in the APOE3 dataset. This was accompanied with limited plaque formation, compact plaques and low levels of oligomeric A β in the mice brain. Recently it was reported that conditional knockout of microRNA miR155 in microglia in APP/PS1 mice leads to activation of interferon-mediated signaling, which was associated with increased phagocytosis and plaque compaction (Yin, Herron, *et al.*, 2023). APOE expression and A β pathology are closely associated in our model which makes it difficult to determine the factors contributing directly or indirectly to the DEG changes seen in microglia and astrocytes. Future studies comparing the effect of APOE deletion in AD versus wildtype mouse models should help to confirm

these findings. Moreover, studying the effect of APOE isoforms in wild type mice on neuronal development and synapse formation, will be of interest as APOE is known to influence synaptic density and to cause behavioural defects in AD mouse (Dumanis *et al.*, 2009; Klein *et al.*, 2010; Koffie *et al.*, 2012).

Depletion of microglia in our model, demonstrated that even though astrocyte derived APOE is sufficient to induce plaque formation by 6 months of age, there was still a significant decrease in amyloid level in the absence of microglia, suggesting that they modulate amyloid plaque formation. We also observed increased levels of APOE in the microglia depleted mouse brains, irrespective of the isoform. APOE co-aggregates with soluble A β species *in vitro* (Xia *et al.*, 2024). Thus, it is possible that APOE-A β co-aggregates are taken up by microglia for clearance, and when microglia is depleted, this leads to increased levels of APOE in the mouse brain.

Limitations of the study include the AAV-mediated transgene expression, which results in overexpression of APOE under a non-native promoter. However, this approach allowed to establish the dose-dependent effects of different APOE isoforms on amyloid deposition, helping to understand the effect of dose versus isoform. Additionally, we did not explore the lipidation status of different APOE isoforms, which influences A β pathology (Koldamova, Staufenbiel and Lefterov, 2005; Wahrle *et al.*, 2005). We also did not investigate possible gender- and ethnicity-specific effects of the different APOE isoforms. Previous reports have demonstrated that gender can affect AD pathology, microglia response and APOE expression (Thomas *et al.*, 2016; Sala Frigerio *et al.*, 2019; Stephen *et al.*, 2019), while the protective and disease causing effects of APOE2 and APOE4 are variable in different ethnic populations (Farrer *et al.*, 1997; Naslavsky *et al.*, 2022). Finally, it was not possible to isolate microglia from the AAV-transduced regions only. This has likely diluted the effect size of changes we see in the microglia at transcriptomic level. This problem was not present for astrocytes where we could use the reporter to specifically enrich for the transduced cells.

In conclusion, we have investigated the cell autonomous and non-cell autonomous effects of the different APOE isoforms on astrocytes and microglia, respectively. It is clear that APOE plays an important role in the interaction between these cell types, with astrocytic APOE being a major driver of the amyloid plaque pathology which in its turn modifies the microglia response. Therefore, we propose that *APOE4* is a “core” gene (Liu, Li and Pritchard, 2019) of AD pathogenesis in the sense that the strong effect on amyloid pathology, a core pathway of AD, explains the strong specific association with AD (odds ratio ~3.7-14.5). The other mechanisms of APOE4 dysfunction probably explain the association with neurodegenerative diseases in general, such as Parkinson’s disease (odds ratio ~1.6-4.19) and Lewy body dementia (odds ratio ~2.4-6.1) (Huang *et al.*, 2006; Irwin *et al.*, 2012; Tsuang *et al.*, 2013; Bras *et al.*, 2014; Guerreiro *et al.*, 2018; Tropea *et al.*, 2018); TDP-43 proteinopathy (odds ratio ~2) (Josephs *et al.*, 2014; Wennberg *et al.*, 2018; Yang *et al.*, 2018); and vascular dementia (odds ratio ~3.13) (Davidson *et al.*, 2006; Sun *et al.*, 2015). Several groups have suggested lowering of APOE expression with APOE-antibodies (Liao *et al.*, 2018; Xiong *et al.*, 2021; Gratuze *et al.*, 2022) or using antisense therapy (Huynh *et al.*, 2017) as a therapeutic option for AD. Our work shows that even in a relative circumscribed and limited part of Alzheimer’s disease pathogenesis, i.e., the formation of amyloid plaques and the microglia response to it, the different isoforms of APOE act in diverse and unanticipated ways, affecting amyloid plaques, A β soluble aggregates, but also the cellular reactions of microglia and astrocytes. We summarized above also the effects of APOE on neurons and blood vessels. A down regulation of APOE expression is not mimicking the protective effects of APOE2, and APOE2 protective action is complex and remains poorly understood. Even with increasing understanding of the pleiotropic role of APOE in the pathogenesis of Alzheimer’s disease it remains difficult to define a precise therapeutic hypothesis based on the deep mechanistic understanding of the role of the different APOE isoforms in the disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mice

The mouse *ApoE* gene is localized on chromosome 7 and consists of four exons and three introns, exon 2-4 contains the coding sequences. *ApoE* knock-out mice were generated using two guides to target the second intron (5'-GUCUCGGCUCUGAACUACAU-3') and the fourth exon (5'-ACUCGGCAGUACCGCAACG-3'). mRNA guides were selected using the CRISPOR web tool (<http://crispor.tefor.net/>). Ribonucleoproteins (RNPs) containing 3 μ M purified Cas9 HiFi protein (Integrated DNA Technologies, IDT) and 4 μ M CRISPR RNA crRNA and trans activating crRNA (IDT) were electroporated (Nepa21) into *Rag2*^{tm1.1Cgn} zygotes by the CBD Mouse Expertise Unit of KU Leuven. Out of 113 embryo's electroporated, 91 embryos were transplanted to foster mothers, 10 pups were born and 3 were positive for the deletion. To establish the *ApoE* knock-out allele (*ApoE*^{em1Bdes}), one founder mouse carrying an 846 bp deletion was selected and crossed with the original strain twice in order to cross out potential off targets events while keeping the background and genetic mutations of the strain. For standard PCR genotyping of the *ApoE* allele, primers 5'-CTCACGGATGGGCACTCAC-3' and 5'-GCTCCCAAGTCACACAAGAA-3' were used, resulting in an amplicon of 331bp for the knock-out allele and in an amplicon of 1117bp for the wild-type allele.

To generate *App*^{tm3.1Tcs} *ApoE*^{em1Bdes} *Rag2*^{tm1.1Cgn} mice (in this study named as *App*^{NL-G-F} x *ApoE*^{-/-} x *Rag2*^{-/-}) and *App*^{tm3.1Tcs} *ApoE*^{em1Bdes} mice (named as *App*^{NL-G-F} x *ApoE*^{-/-}), the mice described above were crossed with *App*^{tm3.1Tcs} knock-in mice harboring the Swedish, Iberian and Arctic FAD mutation as well as the humanized Abeta sequence (Saito *et al.*, 2014). All the data presented in this study are from *App*^{NL-G-F} x *ApoE*^{-/-} mice. For a pilot study to check viral transduction efficiency and specificity, *App*^{NL-G-F} x *ApoE*^{-/-} x *Rag2*^{-/-} mice were used, and data from these are presented in supplementary figures: S1A, S1E, S1F, S2A and S2B.

Mice were kept on a C57Bl6J background and both females and males were included in the study. Mice were housed in cages enriched with wood wool and shavings as bedding and given access to water and food *ad libitum* with a circadian rhythm of 7am-9pm light and 9pm-7am dark. Mice were randomly assigned to experimental groups (unblinded). All experiments were conducted in accordance with institutional and national guidelines and regulations, following approval of Ethical Committee for Animal Experimentation at the University of Leuven (KU Leuven) (permit number P007/2017 and P072/2019).

Intracerebroventricular viral vector injections

Adeno-associated viruses (AAVs) were used to express different human APOE isoforms in mouse astrocytes. Plasmid constructs were designed to express different human APOE alleles under astrocyte specific promoter *Aldh1l1*. Plasmids were created and packaged into AAVs by VectorBuilder (www.vectorbuilder.com). We used AAV2/8 serotype (>10¹³ GC/ml) and the following plasmid constructs: pAAV-ALDH1L1-mCherry (Vectorbuilder ID: VB181123-1160msp), pAAV-ALDH1L1-APOE2-mCherry (Vectorbuilder ID: VB200713-1259snq), pAAV-ALDH1L1-APOE3-mCherry (Vectorbuilder ID: VB200316-1163eeg), pAAV-ALDH1L1-APOE4-mCherry (Vectorbuilder ID: VB200713-1260frb). For intracerebroventricular (ICV) injections, on postnatal day 2/3, the mouse pups were anaesthetized by hypothermia and approximately 2x10¹⁰ infectious particles of AAV (1 μ l per site) were injected into the ventricles with Hamilton syringes bilaterally: halfway between lambda and bregma, 1 mm bilaterally from the midline and 3 mm from the pial surface (Kim *et al.*, 2014). Transduced pups were returned to their home cages until weaning age.

PLX3397 treatment for microglia depletion

For depletion of microglia from mouse brain (Elmore *et al.*, 2014; Spangenberg *et al.*, 2016), PLX3397/Pexidartinib (MedChemExpress #HY-16749) was formulated in standard chow (Bio Services

NL). Modified chow containing PLX3397 (600mg/kg of chow) was administered to the mice for 4 months, starting at 2 months of age before onset of plaque deposition.

RNA extraction and qPCR

For sample collection, mice were euthanized using an overdose of carbon dioxide and perfused with ice-cold 1x DPBS (Gibco, #14190-144). Brains were surgically removed and snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen. Frozen brain tissue was homogenized in PBS (supplemented with cOmplete™ protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche #5056489001)), in a beadmill using FastPrep (MP Biomedicals). TRI reagent (Sigma, #T9424) was added to the supernatant to lyse any remaining cells and 1-bromo-3-chloropropane was used for phase separation. The solution was centrifuged at 12,000 rcf for 15 minutes at 4°C. RNA in the aqueous phase was precipitated in 2-propanol. After centrifugation at 12,000rcf for 10 minutes at 4°C, the RNA pellet was washed with 75% ethanol and solubilized using RNase-free water.

Reverse transcription of mRNA was done using the Superscript II reverse transcriptase (Thermo Fisher Scientific, #18064071). Real-time semi-quantitative PCR was performed using the SensiFast Sybr No-Rox kit (Bioline, #BIO-98020) for cDNA. Following forward and reverse primers were used for human *APOE*: 5'-GTTGCTGGTCACATTCCTGG-3' and 3'-GCAGGTAATCCCAAAGCGAC-5'. Following forward and reverse primers were used for housekeeping genes mouse *Gapdh*: 5'- TTGATGGCAACAATCTCCAC-3' and 3'-CGTCCCGTAGACAAAATGGT-5', and *Actin*: 5'- GTGACGTTGACATCCGTAAAGA-3' and 3'-GCCGGACTCATCGTACTCC-5'.

Protein extraction and MSD-ELISA

For sample collection, mice were euthanized using an overdose of carbon dioxide and perfused with ice-cold 1x DPBS (Gibco, #14190-144). Brains were surgically removed and snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen. Frozen brain tissue was homogenized in PBS (supplemented with cOmplete™ protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche #5056489001)), in a beadmill using FastPrep (MP Biomedicals). The homogenate was centrifuged at 5,000 rcf for 5 minutes at 4°C. The supernatant was ultra-centrifuged at 55,000 rpm (Rotor TLA-110, Beckman Ultra Optima TLX) for 60 minutes at 4°C and the supernatant was used as PBS-soluble fraction. For guanidinium chloride (GuHCl) based extraction, the pellet was resuspended in 6 M GuHCl, 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.6), (supplemented with cOmplete™ protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche)) and sonicated using a micro-tip for 30 s at 10% amplitude (Branson). After incubation for 1 hr at 25 °C, the sample was ultracentrifuged at 70,000 rpm (Rotor TLA-110, Beckman Ultra Optima TLX). The supernatant was then diluted to 0.1 M GuHCl and used as guanidinium-soluble fraction.

A β ₄₂ and hAPOE levels were quantified on MSD 96-well plates (Meso Scale Discovery) using MSD-ELISA. For A β ₄₂, standard 96-well SECTOR plates (MSD #L15XA-3) were coated with LTDA_A β ₄₂ capture antibody (in house generated mouse monoclonal antibody against A β ₄₂ in collaboration with Maarten Dewilde). After overnight incubation at 4 °C, the plates were rinsed with PBS 0.05% Tween 20 and blocked with casein buffer (PBS with 1% casein, pH 7.4) for 4 h at room temperature. Synthetic human A β ₄₂ dilutions were used as standards. Standards and samples were preincubated with LTDA_hA β N labeled with a sulfo-TAG detection antibody (in house generated mouse monoclonal antibody against the N-terminal sequence of human A β , in collaboration with Maarten Dewilde), in casein buffer for 5 minutes at room temperature. The blocked assay plate was rinsed five times with PBS 0.05% Tween 20, and the sample and detection antibody mix were added and incubated overnight at 4 °C. For hAPOE, we used R-PLEX Human APOE Assay kit (MSD #K1512IR-2) and total APOE level in each sample was measured as sum of APOE level in PBS-soluble and Guanidine-soluble fractions. Briefly, GOLD 96-well Small Spot Streptavidin SECTOR plates (MSD) were coated with biotinylated capture antibody, for 1 hour at room temperature. The plates were rinsed with PBS 0.05% Tween 20, followed by addition of standards and samples diluted in assay buffer and incubated for 1 hour at room temperature. After

rinsing, detection antibody was added and incubated for 1 hour at room temperature. For measurement, the plates were rinsed, and 2x Read T buffer (MSD) (for A β 42) or GOLD Read Buffer B (MSD) (for hAPOE) was added, and plates were read on an MSD Sector Imager 2400A.

SiMPull assay for soluble A β aggregate quantification

Soluble oligomeric aggregates of A β were extracted from frozen brain tissue. Post thawing, soaking extraction was performed with a protocol modified from a previously published method (Hong *et al.*, 2018). Briefly, brain samples were added to 1.5 mL Eppendorf Protein LoBind[®] tubes and soaking buffer containing 124 mM NaCl, 2.8 mM KCl, 1.25 mM NaH₂PO₄, 26 mM NaHCO₃, 5 mM EDTA, 1 mM EGTA, 5 μ g/mL leupeptin, 5 μ g/mL aprotinin, 2 μ g/mL pepstatin, 5 mM NaF, 20 μ g/mL Pefabloc[®] SC protease inhibitor (Merck, #1429868001) and PhosSTOPTM phosphatase inhibitor tablet (Merck, #4906845001) was added to each sample. Samples were placed on a rotary shaker for 4.5 hours at 4 °C and then centrifuged at 2000 rcf for 10 minutes at 4 °C. Following the initial centrifugation, the supernatant was centrifuged again for 2 hours at 4°C, at 17000 rcf. Then the supernatant was aliquoted, snap frozen in liquid nitrogen, and stored at -80 °C.

Single-molecule pull-down coverslip preparation was performed as previously described (Emin *et al.*, 2022). Briefly, neutravidin (0.2 mg/ml) in PBS with 0.05% Tween 20 (PBST) was added to glass coverslips covalently mounted with polyethylene glycol (PEG) and biotin for 10 minutes, followed by two wash steps with PBST and once with PBS with 1% Tween 20 (1%T). Afterwards biotinylated 6E10 (BioLegend, #803007, 10 nM) was added for 15 min, followed by two wash steps with PBST and once with 1%T. The soaked brain samples were added and incubated overnight at 4 °C followed by two wash steps with PBST and once with 1%T. The coverslips were then incubated with labelled Alexa Fluoro 647 conjugated 6E10 (BioLegend Cat. 803020, 500 pM) for 45 min, followed by two wash steps with PBST and once with 1%T. A second PDMS gasket was added to the slide to increase the well volume and 8 μ L's of PBS was added to prevent drying of the wells.

Then the coverslips were imaged on a purpose built (Emin *et al.*, 2022) TIRF microscope using a 638 nm laser, with 50 milliseconds of exposure for 50 frames for each field of view. A minimum of 9 field of views were acquired from each well.

Immunohistochemistry (IHC)

For sample collection, mice were euthanized using an overdose of carbon dioxide and perfused with ice-cold 1x DPBS (Gibco, #14190-144). Brains were surgically removed, post-fixed in 4 % paraformaldehyde (PFA) overnight and cut into 40 μ m thick sections on vibratome (Leica VT1000S). A β plaques were detected by staining with X-34 (Sigma #SML1954). Nuclei staining was performed using DAPI (Sigma #D9542). The following antibodies were used for immunostaining: rabbit anti-RFP (Takara, #632496, 1:500); rabbit anti-Iba1 (Wako, #019-19741, 1:500); guinea pig anti-NeuN (Synaptic Systems, #266-004, 1:300); mouse anti-Apc (Millipore, #OP80, 1:200); guinea pig anti-GFAP (Synaptic Systems #173-004, 1:1000); guinea pig anti-Iba1 (Synaptic Systems, #234-004, 1:500); rabbit anti-ApoE (Atlas Antibodies, #HPA065539, 1:500); rabbit anti-Ctsd (Santa-cruz, #sc10725, 1:200); rat anti-Cd68 (Biolegend, #137001, 1:100); donkey anti-rabbit Alexa 488 (Invitrogen, #A21206, 1:500); donkey anti-rat Alexa 488 (Invitrogen #A21208, 1:500); donkey anti-mouse Alexa 488 (Invitrogen #A21202, 1:500); donkey anti-rabbit Alexa 594 (Invitrogen #A21207, 1:500); donkey anti-guinea pig Cy[™]5 (Jackson Immuno, #706-175-148, 1:500). Antigen retrieval was performed by microwave boiling the sections in 10mM tri-Sodium Citrate buffer pH 6.0 (VWR). After rinsing with PBS, the free-floating sections were blocked and permeabilized using 10% donkey serum (Jackson Immunolabs, #017-000-121) and 0.3% Triton X-100. Primary antibodies, diluted to required concentrations, were then added to the sections and incubated overnight at 4 °C. The sections were washed using PBS and secondary antibodies conjugated with fluorophores were added for 2 hours at room temperature. Finally, after washing with PBS, sections were mounted on the slides with Glycergel (DAKO). Confocal images with z-stacks (1.5

$\mu\text{m} / 1 \mu\text{m}$ step size) were obtained using a Nikon AX inverted confocal microscope driven by NIS (4.30) software. All images were acquired with 20x (field of view: $880.42 \times 880.42 \mu\text{m}$) or 40x (field of view: $438.88 \times 438.88 \mu\text{m}$) or 60x objectives (field of view: $292.3 \times 292.3 \mu\text{m}$). For excitation 405 nm, 488 nm, 561 nm, 640 nm laser lines were used. Raw images were processed in ImageJ (1.53t) software. Z-stacks were converted to Maximum Intensity Projections for quantifications, unless otherwise specified. For representative images provided in Figures, brightness was adjusted, if necessary (by equal measure across all experimental groups), for better visualization.

Plaque IHC Quantification

Flattened tiff files from 20x and 40x images were used for quantifying X-34 positive amyloid plaques. Individual plaques larger than ~ 4 micron were segmented from 20x and 40x IHC image using an interactive machine learning approach, implemented through ImageJ and the Labkit plugin (Schindelin *et al.*, 2012; Arzt *et al.*, 2022). In this method a random forest pixel classifier was trained, with $\sum_{n=0}^3 2^n$ values for σ and the original image, gaussian blur, difference of gaussians, gaussian gradient magnitude, Laplacian of gaussian, hessian eigenvalues filters of the image as inputs. After segmenting, image features were extracted using a python pipeline. Briefly, the size, location and gray-scale co-occurrence matrix of the segmented plaques were calculated using the scikit-learn imaging library (Van Der Walt *et al.*, 2014). Next, Angular Second Moment (ASM) of the gray-scale-co-occurrence matrix was calculated as an estimate of amyloid plaque compactness (Haralick, Shanmugam and Dinstein, 1973). ASM is a measure of local image homogeneity, a higher value being consistent with a more homogenous plaque with fewer transitions between light and dark zones. Haralick's features are a well-established set of rotation invariant image statistics that have been used in medical classification issues across many fields and imaging modalities (Doyle *et al.*, 2008; Gnep *et al.*, 2017; Hapsari *et al.*, 2022). Among the different Haralick's features, ASM was found to be the statistic most congruent with the visual differences between more diffuse and more dense plaques.

Microglia IHC Quantification

3D z-stacks from raw 40x images were used for segmenting Iba1-positive microglia. Individual microglia were segmented using a custom pipeline combining a state-of-the-art machine learning model with established image processing methods. This more tailored solution was chosen over more prevalent methods like Imaris as it was unable to accurately segment physically touching and overlapping cell bodies with intertwining branches, in the absence of nuclei staining. Instead, the established method Labkit was found to be particularly good at identifying which pixels belonged to microglia but failed to distinguish individual microglia from each-other, especially around plaques, where microglia tend to cluster densely. On the other hand, we found that state-of-the-art Cellpose machine learning β was unable to segment the full cell including its processes (Stringer *et al.*, 2021). To achieve the highest accuracy, a pipeline was built to combine the strengths of both methods. First, the pre-trained 'cyto' Cellpose model was manually fine-tuned to segment the cell bodies and find their centroids. Secondly, all pixels belonging to microglia were identified using Labkit. A classifier was trained with $\sum_{n=1}^6 2^n$ for σ and the original image, gaussian blur, difference of gaussians, gaussian gradient magnitude, Laplacian of gaussian, hessian eigenvalues, mean and max filters of the image as inputs. The resulting semantic segmentation mask was tentatively split into cell-bodies and processes. We then performed minor closing operations on the process mask to fix small continuity errors which would otherwise cause interruptions in the microglial processes. These two masks were then recombined.

Both the Labkit segmentation mask and the Cellpose segmentation mask were then subjected to the Exact Euclidean distance transformation which resulted in masks where the value of each pixel equals its distance to the edge of the binary mask. These two distance masks were combined in a weighted sum so the Cellpose masked areas were of greater value than the Labkit areas. Finally, the watershedding algorithm was performed using the Cellpose centroids as local minima, to retrieve individually labelled microglia. (Fig S4A). Individually labelled microglia were then digitally traced using the APP2 plugin for VAA3D and the convex area of the cell, as well as the total length of its processes

were calculated to quantify their morphological changes (Peng *et al.*, 2010; Xiao and Peng, 2013). For counting number of microglia associated to each plaque, 3d z-stacks were flattened to tiffs post microglia segmentation. X-34-positive plaques were thresholded and segmented as described above. Any microglia whose centroid was located within X-34-positive thresholded plaque area and up to 5 μm outside a plaque's edge was considered as plaque-associated microglia. For each microglia, the mean distance to its three nearest neighbours were also calculated as a measure of clustering.

FACS isolation of microglia and astrocytes

For sample collection, 6 months old mice were anaesthetized using CO₂ chamber and perfused with ice-cold 1x DPBS (Gibco, #14190-144). Each mouse brain, excluding cerebellum and olfactory bulbs were dissected and placed in FACS buffer (1x DPBS, 2% FCS and 2 mM EDTA) + 5 μM Actinomycin D (ActD, Sigma, #A1410-5MG) for transcriptomics. Brains were mechanically and enzymatically dissociated using Miltenyi neural tissue dissociation kit P (Miltenyi, #130-092-628) supplemented with 5 μM ActD. Next, samples were passed through a 70 μm strainer (BD2 Falcon), washed in 10 ml of ice-cold FACS buffer + 5 μM ActD and spun at 300 rcf for 15 minutes at 4 °C. Note that 5 μM ActD was kept during collection and enzymatic dissociation of the tissue to preserve transcriptional state and prevent artificial induction stress-response genes during tissue dissociation (Perocchi *et al.*, 2007; Marsh *et al.*, 2022). ActD was removed from the myelin removal step to prevent toxicity derived from long-term exposure. Following dissociation, myelin was removed by resuspending pelleted cells into 30% isotonic Percoll (GE Healthcare, #17-5445-02) and centrifuging at 300 rcf for 15 minutes at 4 °C. Accumulating layers of myelin and cellular debris were discarded and Fc receptors were blocked in FcR blocking solution (1:10, Miltenyi, #130-092-575) in cold FACS buffer for 10 minutes at 4°C. Next, cells were washed in 5 ml of FACS buffer and pelleted cells split into two suspensions (one each for astrocyte and microglia sorting), and incubated with the following antibodies: for microglia- PE-CD11b (Miltenyi, #130-113-806, 1:50), BV421-CD45 (BD, #563890, 1:500); for astrocytes- APC-ACSA2 (Miltenyi, #130-116-142, 1:200), BV421-CD11b (BD, #562605, 1:500), PE-O4 (Miltenyi, #130-117-357, 1:50); in cold FACS buffer for 30 minutes at 4 °C. TotalSeq™-A cell hashing antibodies (1:500, Biolegend) and viability dye (eFluor 780, Thermo Fisher Scientific, #65-0865-14) were also added to both fractions during the incubation step. After incubation, cells were washed, and the pellet was resuspended in 500 μl of FACS buffer and passed through 35 μm strainer prior sorting. For isolating microglia, cell suspension was loaded into the input chamber of MACSQuant Tyto Cartridge and cells were sorted on MACSQuant Tyto Cell Sorter at 4 °C, based on CD11b-positive and CD45-low populations. For isolating AAV-transduced astrocytes, cells were sorted on Aria Fusion, based on negative gating for O4 and CD11b populations, followed by positive gating for double-positive ACSA2 and mCherry populations. FACS data was analysed using FCS express software.

Single cell library preparation and sequencing

For single-cell RNA sequencing microglia and astrocytes, 20,000-30,000 cells of each type from each mouse were sorted as described above and diluted to a final concentration of 1000 cells/ μl . All the samples were individually hashed using TotalSeq™-A cell hashing antibodies, 3000 cells/animal were pooled and loaded onto the Chromium Next GEM Chip G (PN #2000177). The DNA library preparations were generated following manufacturers' instructions (CG000204 Chromium Next GEM Single Cell 3' Reagent Kits v3.1). In parallel the hashtag oligo libraries were prepared according to manufacturers' instructions (BioLegend - TotalSeq™-A Antibodies and Cell Hashing with 10x Single Cell 3' Reagent Kit v3 3.1 Protocol) using 16cycles for the index PCR. From the 4 experimental groups (APOEKO, APOE2, APOE3, and APOE4), a total of 8 libraries (APOEKO_astrocytes, APOE2_astrocytes, APOE3_astrocytes, APOE4_astrocytes, APOEKO_microglia, APOE2_microglia, APOE3_microglia, APOE4_microglia), containing 22 biological replicates (n(APOEKO)= 2, n(APOE2)= 3, n(APOE3)=3, n(APOE4)= 3), were sequenced (service provided by BGI Genomics, China) targeting 90% mRNA and 10% hashtag oligo library (50,000 reads/cell) on a DNBSEQ-G400 (MGI Tech) platform with the recommended read lengths by 10X Genomics workflow.

Analysis of single-cell RNA sequencing datasets

Alignment and analysis pipeline

Raw BCL files were aligned to a modified GRCm39 mouse genome, which was appended with the human APOE gene. We used Bedtools 2.27.1 to extract the human APOE sequence and a thousand base buffer from GRCh38 (Quinlan and Hall, 2010). This was then appended to the murine GRCm39 genome in an artificial chromosome. The resulting genome was then filtered using the *mkgtf* function from Cellranger (6.1.2), in accordance with 10x guidelines (Zheng *et al.*, 2017) and subsequently processed into a functional reference using cellranger *mkref*. Finally, each of the eight scRNAseq libraries were aligned to a custom genome using Cellranger's count function which matches each transcript to its corresponding gene using the STAR aligner (Dobin *et al.*, 2013). Raw count matrices were imported in R (v4.3.3) for data analysis. Datasets were analysed using R packages: *Seurat* (4.4) (Hao *et al.*, 2021), *scater* (1.30.1) (McCarthy *et al.*, 2017), *clustree* (0.5.1) (Zappia and Oshlack, 2018), and *SuperExactTest* (1.1) (Wang, Zhao and Zhang, 2015). Visualizations were done using functions from *Seurat*, *SuperExactTest* or *ggplot2* (3.5).

Quality control of cells and samples

In this overexpression model, since APOE is under a constitutive promoter, and hence not a part of the normal transcriptional regulatory networks, we excluded human APOE gene expression from both astrocyte and microglia datasets prior to the following steps.

For each library of microglia, low-level quality control was done by first filtering out cells with < 200 genes detected and genes expressed in less than 3 cells, from the raw counts matrix. Subsequent filtering involved three steps. Step 1: Cell hashing information was added to each library using *Seurat::HTODemux()* function to assign each cell as either singlets, doublets or negatives. Only singlets were retained, as doublets and singlets had abnormally high and low number of reads, respectively, indicative of poor-quality cells. Step 2: Libraries from the 4 experimental groups were merged using *Seurat::merge()* function, to have in total 23,495 cells (Fig. S9A). Cell clustering was performed using the pipeline described below. Cell type annotation was done using *seurat::AddModuleScore()* to assign cell scores based on previously identified signatures for different brain cell types (Zeisel *et al.*, 2018). ~9% of cells had non-microglial identity with half of those having macrophage identity. Contaminating cell types were identified (Figs. S9A, B) as macrophages (microglia QC Cluster 4), endothelial cells (microglia QC Cluster 5), mix of astrocyte and microglial cells (microglia QC Cluster 6), monocytes (microglia QC Clusters 7 and 9), and oligodendrocytes (microglia QC Cluster 10). Out of the rest ~10% separated out as a cluster (microglia QC Cluster 2) with low number of reads and gene count (Fig. S9C). Step 3: After filtering out these clusters, each library was split into individual ones and quality control was refined with an additional step using *scater::isOutlier()* function. Here cells with number of reads or genes or percentage of mitochondrial genes (%mito), outside n median absolute deviation ($n(\text{reads}) = +/- 4$, $n(\text{genes}) = - 4$, $n(\%mito) = + 5$) from library median, were removed. Finally, 18,569 microglia were retained for analysis as good-quality cells.

For astrocytes, the same steps as described above with few modifications were executed. Step 1: Cell hashing did not work efficiently for astrocytes, as a good proportion of cells identified as negatives had read counts in the same range as Singlet cells. Thus, we used the other two steps to filter out low-quality cells. Step 2: Libraries from the 4 experimental groups were merged to have in total 32,982 cells (Fig. S9D). After cell type annotation as described above, ~7% of cells had non-astrocyte identity. Contaminating cell types were identified (Figs. S9D, E) as ependymal cells (astrocyte QC Cluster 5), mural cells (astrocyte QC Cluster 7), microglia (astrocyte QC Cluster 9), endothelial cells (astrocyte QC Cluster 10) and a population of undetermined identity (astrocyte QC Cluster 8). Out of the rest, ~31% separated out as clusters (astrocyte QC Clusters 1 and 6) with low number of reads and gene count (Fig. S9F). Step 3: After filtering out these clusters, each libraries were split into individual ones using *Seurat::SplitObject()* and quality control was refined with an additional step using *scater::isOutlier()*

function. Here cells with number of reads or genes or percentage of mitochondrial genes (%mito), outside n median absolute deviation ($n(\text{reads}) = \pm 2.5$, $n(\text{genes}) = - 2.5$, $n(\% \text{mito}) = + 5$) from library median, were removed. Finally, 18,667 astrocytes were retained for analysis as good-quality cells.

Library Integration and Cell Clustering

To remove batch effects between libraries while cell clustering, the Seurat Object was split into individual libraries using `Seurat::SplitObject()`. Each libraries were individually normalized (`Seurat::NormalizeData`) and variable genes identified (`Seurat::FindVariableFeatures`). Genes that are repeatedly variable across libraries were selected for integration (`Seurat::SelectIntegrationFeatures()`). Integration anchors were identified (`Seurat::FindIntegrationAnchors()`) and batch correction was performed (`Seurat::IntegrateData()`). After scaling and centering genes (`Seurat::ScaleData()`) in the integrated dataset, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed. n dimensions from the PCA ($n(\text{astrocytes}) = 50$; $n(\text{microglia}) = 40$) were selected for identifying clusters (`Seurat::FindNeighbors()` and `Seurat::FindClusters()`). To avoid over-clustering or under-clustering, multiple resolutions were used for the `FindCluster()` function and `clustree::clustree()` was used for selecting an optimum resolution (astrocytes = 0.7; microglia = 0.4). For visualization of clusters, dimensionality reduction by Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP), was performed with the `Seurat::RunUMAP()` function. Cluster markers for astrocytes and microglia were identified using `Seurat::FindAllMarkers()` function which calculates differential expression for each cluster against the rest. Astrocyte clusters were scored using `seurat::AddModuleScore()`, for markers from previously published genesets of astrocyte cell states (Zamanian *et al.*, 2012; Hasel *et al.*, 2021), plaque-induced genes (PIGs) (Chen *et al.*, 2020) and AD risk genes (Bellenguez *et al.*, 2022).

Differential Expression

For both astrocytes (telencephalon subtype) and microglia, differential expression was performed between the 4 experimental groups (each of APOEKO, APOE2 and APOE4 compared to APOE3), using `Seurat::FindMarkers()`. Genes expressed in at least 5% of cells were calculated. For calculating p-values, MAST was used which is a GLM-framework that treats cellular detection rate as a covariate. Since there were differences in the gender ratio between the groups, gender identity was regressed out during differential expression using `latent.vars` parameter. Post-analysis, genes with their adjusted P value < 0.05 (post-hoc, Bonferroni correction) and $|\log(\text{fold-change})| > 0.2$ were considered as significant. `SuperExactTest` (Wang, Zhao and Zhang, 2015) was used to calculate statistical significance (Tables S3, S6) and visualize overlap of differentially expressed genes while comparing each group with APOE3. Size of background gene population (n) for `SuperExactTest` was collected from total number of genes in the Seurat object for astrocytes and microglia library ($n(\text{astrocytes})=25321$, $n(\text{microglia})=23819$). Volcano plots and quadrant plots using `ggplot2::ggplot()` and dot plots using `Seurat::DotPlot()` were used to visualize differentially expressed genes between the groups.

Gene Ontology (GO) Enrichment Analysis

For astrocytes and microglia, cluster markers identified, as mentioned above, was used to perform functional enrichment analysis. This was done using `g:Profiler` web interface (<https://biit.cs.ut.ee/gprofiler/gost>), where the cluster markers were queried against GO biological process database, with `g:SCS` multiple testing correction method applying significance threshold of 0.05 (Kolberg *et al.*, 2023). Bar plots using `ggplot2::ggplot()` was used to visualize the top 10 significantly enriched terms for astrocyte clusters a0 and a6.

Statistical analysis

Number of samples included in each experiment is included in the results section/figure legends. Sample size estimation was based on pilot experiments. All statistical comparisons were performed in Graphpad Prism (v10.0.2) or R (v4.3.3). Statistical test used for each experiment is reported in the figure legends. For analysis where individual plaques or microglia were plotted as data points, mixed

effects models were used to account for the variability between individual mice and Q-Q plots were used to assess the normality of the residuals, using the lme4 package for mixed effects models and the “estimated marginal means” package in R. For comparison of ASM values in Figs. 2 and 5, the linear mixed-effects model was used with mouse ID and diameter of plaques as confounding factors. ASM response variable was also log-transformed to improve the normality of the residuals. Differential abundance of plaque-associated microglia around individual plaques in Fig. 4 was tested using binomial generalized linear mixed-effects model with mouse ID as confounding factor. Morphological differences between plaque-associated microglia and non-plaque-associated microglia in Fig S3 was tested using linear mixed-effects model with mouse ID as confounding factor. Differences in total number of differentially expressed genes between groups (compared to APOE3) was tested using Fisher’s exact test with Bonferroni correction of p-values. Enrichment of plaque-induced genes (PIGs) (Chen *et al.*, 2020) in intersection of differentially expressed genes in microglia dataset was tested using hypergeometric test with Bonferroni correction of p-values.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Raw data used for this research article is available upon request to the corresponding authors. Single cell RNA sequencing data generated in this study are available at Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) database with accession number GSE252454.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

P.P., A.M.A. and B.D.S. conceived and designed the study and planned the experiments. M.F. checked all the bioinformatics data and their interpretations. P.P. performed experiments and analyzed data together with B.D.S. and A.M.A.. D.M. provided bioinformatic support and analyzed data together with M.F. E.F. performed SimPull experiments, under the supervision of D.K.. L.W., J.L., and S.P., assisted with single cell RNA-sequencing experiments. L.S. generated the mouse lines. D.S. assisted with generation of AAV vectors. A.S. assisted with immunohistochemistry experiments. R.M. and S.B. assisted with designing and execution of microglia depletion studies. All authors discussed the results and commented on the manuscript

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

B.D.S. is or has been a consultant for Eli Lilly, Biogen, Janssen Pharmaceutica, Eisai, AbbVie and other companies. B.D.S is also a scientific founder of Augustine Therapeutics and a scientific founder and stockholder of Muna Therapeutics.

FIGURE LEGENDS

Main Figures

Figure 1. Expression of APOE in astrocytes is sufficient to restore fibrillar A β plaque pathology. (A) AAV2/8 vector was used to express human APOE under the ALDH1L1 promoter. AAV particles were injected via ICV in *App^{NL-G-F} x ApoE^{-/-}* neonatal mice on postnatal days two or three (P2/P3). Samples were collected for analysis at 6 months of age. (B) IF images of AAV-transduced cortical regions (see Fig. S2A) at 6 months of age. mCherry (red) shows the transduced astrocytes. X-34 (white) shows the fibrillar plaque deposits. Scale bar: 100 μ m. (C) Bar plots showing (i) number of X-34+ plaques per field of view (FOV, 20x magnification) and (ii) area of X-34+ plaques (as fraction of total area in FOV, 20x magnification), in the AAV-transduced cortical region. Data points show mean value of 3 fields of view per mouse (n= 6-10 mice per group). (D) Bar plot showing total APOE levels in brain homogenates measured by MSD-ELISA. Data points show mean value for 2 technical replicates per mouse (n= 8-10 mice per group). ns = non-significant. (E) Scatter plot showing linear regression between total APOE levels (x-axis) and corresponding guanidine-soluble A β_{42} levels (y-axis), measured by MSD-ELISA. Data points show mean value of 2 technical replicates per mouse (n= 8-10 mice per group). (F) TIRF images of mAb 6E10-positive A β aggregates (white) captured from soaked brain fraction using SimPull technique. Scale bar: 10 μ m (G) Quantification of mAb 6E10-positive A β aggregates. Data points show mean value for 3 technical replicates per mouse (n= 4 mice per group, 9 field of views per technical replicate). Colour legend for experimental groups in (D), (E) and (G) are indicated in (C). **Statistical tests:** Data presented as mean \pm SEM (C), (D), and (G). One-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparison test (C), (D), and (G). Significance shown for pairwise comparisons *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001, ****p < 0.0001

Figure 2. APOE expression and astrocyte cell-states in *App^{NL-G-F}* mouse brain. (A) UMAP plot showing 18,667 astrocytes (mCherry+/Acsa2+) sorted from 6 months old mouse brains from the four experimental groups (n= 2 or 3 mice per group). Different sub-populations identified have been assigned Cluster numbers. Dotted lines separate the clusters with telencephalon astrocyte signatures. (B) Dot plot showing the top 10 differentially expressed genes in each cluster. Colour scale indicates normalized expression level, scaled per gene (z-score). Dot size indicates percentage of cells, in each cluster, expressing the gene. (C) Bar plot showing the proportion of astrocytes from each experimental group present in the different clusters. (D) Bar plot showing top 10 significantly enriched GO Biological process terms for Clusters a0 and a6, ordered according to $-\log_{10}$ (adjusted p-value). **Statistical tests:** g:SCS multiple testing correction method (Kolberg *et al.*, 2023) in (D) applying significance threshold of 0.05.

Figure 3. APOE isoforms modulate astrocyte transcriptome in *App^{NL-G-F}* mouse brain. (A) Upset plot showing number of differentially expressed genes (UP or DOWN) in telencephalon astrocytes from each experimental group, compared to APOE3 group. Bar plot shows the number of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) common between different DE analyses (overlapping sets indicated by black dots in column below the bars). Bars are colored according to statistical significance of intersection of DEGs. (B) Volcano plot showing differentially expressed genes between *APOEKO* telencephalon astrocytes and APOE3 expressing telencephalon astrocytes. Datapoints for significant genes are coloured (Red for UP and blue for DOWN). Significance assigned based on $|\text{Log}_2(\text{Fold Change})| > 0.2$ and adjusted p-value < 0.05. (C) Violin plot showing normalized gene expression for *Pde10a* in telencephalon astrocytes from the experimental groups. (D) Quadrant plot comparing differential expression of genes in telencephalon astrocytes in APOE2 vs APOE3 (along x-axis) and in APOE4 vs APOE3 (along y-axis). Colours in legend key indicate significance of genes up- or downregulated in APOE2 or APOE4 or both. Significance of differentially expressed genes based on $|\text{Log}_2(\text{Fold Change})| > 0.2$ and adjusted p-value < 0.05). Pearson's correlation, R = 0.5. **Statistical tests:** MAST differential expression test in (A), (B) and (D), p-values were adjusted with Bonferroni correction based on the total number of genes in the dataset. SuperExactTest (Wang, Zhao and Zhang, 2015) in (A).

Figure 4. *Apo*e-deficient microglia mount reactive responses to fibrillar amyloid plaques. (A) IF images of AAV transduced cortical regions (see Fig. S2A), at 6 months of age. mCherry (red) shows the transduced astrocytes. X-34 staining (white) shows the fibrillar plaque deposits. Co-staining with anti-Iba1 antibody shows microglial cells (green). Scale bar: 100 μ m. (B) IF images of AAV-APOE4 transduced cortical regions (see Fig. S2A) at 6 months of age. X-34 staining (white) shows the fibrillar plaque deposits. Co-staining with anti-Iba1 antibody shows microglial cells (green) and anti-Cd68 antibody shows phagocytic structures (red) inside microglia surrounding plaques. Scale bar: 100 μ m. (C) IF images of AAV-APOE4 transduced cortical regions at 6 months of age. X-34 staining (white) shows the fibrillar plaque deposits. Co-staining with anti-Iba1 antibody shows microglia (green) and anti-CtsD antibody shows lysosomal structures (red) inside clustered microglia surrounding plaques. Scale bar: 100 μ m. (D) (i) Bar plot showing total number of microglia per field of view (FOV, 40x magnification) in AAV transduced regions. Data points show mean value of 3 fields of view per mouse (n= 6-7 mice per group). (ii) Scatter plot showing linear regression between area of X-34+ staining (as fraction of total area in FOV) and total number of microglia (solid triangle), or number of plaque-associated microglia (solid circle), or number of non-plaque-associated microglia (hollow circle), for each experimental group. Data points show mean value 3 fields of view per mouse (n= 6-7 mice per group). Shape legends for different categories of microglia in (i) and (ii) are indicated. One-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparison test in (Di). Significance shown for pairwise comparisons **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001, ****p < 0.0001

Figure 5. Astrocyte-derived APOE initiates, and microglia modify, fibrillar A β plaque pathology. (A) Experimental design illustrating PLX3397 treatment for microglial depletion in *App*^{NL-G-F} x *Apo*e^{-/-} mice. Treatment started at 2 months of age by mixing PLX3397 (600mg/kg) in chow and samples were collected for analysis at 6 months of age. (B) IF images of AAV transduced cortical regions (see Fig. S2A) at 6 months of age from control (top row) and PLX3397-treated (bottom row) groups. mCherry (red) shows the transduced astrocytes. X-34 staining (white) shows the fibrillar plaque deposits in mouse brain cortex. Co-staining with anti-Iba1 antibody shows microglial cells (green). Scale bar: 100 μ m. (C) Bar plots showing number of X-34+ plaques per field of view (FOV, 20x magnification) and area of X-34+ plaques (as fraction of total area in FOV, 20x magnification), in the AAV-transduced cortical region for (i) APOE2, (ii) APOE3 and (iii) APOE4 groups and their respective PLX3397 treated groups. Data points show mean value of 3 fields of view per mouse (n= 4-10 mice per group). Data points for control non-treated groups are the same as shown in Fig. 1C (D) Scatter plot showing linear regression between total APOE levels (x-axis) and corresponding guanidine-soluble A β ₄₂ levels (y-axis), measured by MSD-ELISA for PLX3397-treated and control mice from (i) APOE2, (ii) APOE3 and (iii) APOE4 groups. Data points show mean value for each mouse (n= 4-10 mice per group. 2 technical replicates per mouse). Data points for control non-treated groups are the same as shown in Fig. 1E. **Statistical tests:** Data represented as mean \pm SEM in (C). Unpaired t-test in (C). p-values are indicated.

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. AAV-mediated transduction enables expression of APOE specifically in astrocytes in vivo. (A) IF image of AAV transduced mouse brain coronal sections at 2 months of age showing distribution of transduced astrocytes (mCherry in red) in cortex and subcortical areas (in *App*^{NL-G-F} x *Rag*2^{-/-} x *Apo*e^{-/-} mice. Scale bar: 500 μ m. (B) IF image of AAV transduced cortical region (see Fig. S2A) of 6 months old *App*^{NL-G-F} x *Apo*e^{-/-} mouse brain, showing mCherry (red) co-localizing with astrocyte marker Aldh111 (green). Image below shows a zoomed (5x) view of merged image indicated by the inset box of white dashed-lines. Scale bar: 100 μ m. (C) Contour plot from flow cytometry analysis showing (i) density distribution of mCherry+ and Acsa2+ astrocytes, split to show (ii) proportion of mCherry+ cells in total Acsa2+ cells, and (iii) proportion of Acsa2+ astrocytes in total mCherry+ cells, in 6 months old *App*^{NL-G-F} x *Apo*e^{-/-} mouse brain. Colour scale indicates count density for each contour bin. (D) IF images of AAV transduced cortical region (see Fig. S2A) of 6 months old *App*^{NL-G-F} x *Apo*e^{-/-} mouse brain. mCherry (red) shows the transduced cells. Co-staining with anti-Iba1 antibody showing microglia (cyan) (Note that this is the same image as S1B and co-staining was done with Aldh111); with anti-Apc antibody showing

oligodendrocytes cells (green); with anti-NeuN antibody showing neurons (white) (Note that Apc and NeuN panels are shown from the same image as these markers were co-stained in the same slide). Images below show zoomed in (5x) views indicated by the inset box of white dashed-lines. Scale bar: 100 μm . **(E)** IF images of AAV transduced cortical region (see Fig. S2A) of 6 months old *App^{NL-G-F} x Rag2^{-/-} x Apoe^{-/-}* mouse brain, showing APOE3 (green) co-localizing with mCherry+ (red). Scale bar: 100 μm . **(F)** Bar plot showing human APOE mRNA levels at 6 months of age in mouse brain homogenates measured by semiquantitative real-time PCR. Data points show mean value for 3 technical replicates per mouse (n= 3 mice per group). ns = non-significant. **Statistical tests:** Data presented as mean \pm SEM in (F). One-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparison test (F). Significance shown for pairwise comparisons: ****p < 0.0001

Figure S2. Astrocyte-derived APOE leads to fibrillar A β plaque formation in vivo. **(A)** IF images showing AAV transduced (red) regions in the cortex and the associated distribution of X-34+ fibrillar plaque deposits (white) in 6 months old *App^{NL-G-F} x Rag2^{-/-} x Apoe^{-/-}* mice. Scale bar: 500 μm **(B)** IF images showing distribution of X-34+ fibrillar plaque deposits (white) and Iba1+ microglia clustering (green) in cortical region in 6 months old *App^{NL-G-F} x Rag2^{-/-}* mice (top panel). Absence of fibrillar plaque deposits and clustered microglia in cortical region of 6 months old *App^{NL-G-F} x Rag2^{-/-} x Apoe^{-/-}* mouse brain (bottom panel). Scale bar: 500 μm . **(C)** IF images of AAV transduced cortical region of 6 months old *App^{NL-G-F} x Apoe^{-/-}* mouse brain, showing APOE3 (green) co-localizing with mCherry+ (red) astrocytes and X-34+ (white) fibrillar plaque deposits. Scale bar: 100 μm .

Figure S3. Astrocyte-derived APOE modulates the size and compactness of fibrillar A β plaques. **(A)** Composite tile showing individual X-34+ fibrillar plaques, with increasing plaque size (measured in diameter) along the x-axis and increasing compactness (measured in Angular Second Moment (ASM) value) along the y-axis. Higher ASM values correlate with higher compactness. **(B)** Stacked bar plot showing proportion of X-34+ fibrillar plaques from APOE2, APOE3 and APOE4 groups in different size categories (diameter in μm) along the x-axis. Lower limit for plaque size set to 5 μm in diameter. Size categories used: small (5-20 μm diameter), medium (20-40 μm diameter) and large (above 40 μm diameter). **(C)** Box plot showing ASM values as an estimate of plaque compactness in APOE2, APOE3 and APOE4 groups. Size categories used: (i) small (5-20 μm diameter), (ii) medium (20-40 μm diameter) and (iii) large (above 40 μm diameter). Data points show value for individual plaques (n= 8-10 mice per group. 3 FOV per mouse). **Statistical tests:** Data presented as median and interquartile range \pm values within 1.5 times the interquartile range (C). Linear mixed effects model with Tukey's HSD test in (C) done at mouse sample level. Significance shown for pairwise comparisons **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001, ****p < 0.0001

Figure S4. APOE expression modulates astrocyte cell-states in *App^{NL-G-F}* mouse brain. **(A)** UMAP plot (same as Figure 6a), showing expression of markers for non-telencephalon (*Agt*, *Slc6a11*, *Slac6a9*) and telencephalon (*Mfge8*, *Lhx2*, *Ppp1r3g*) astrocytes. Colour scale indicates normalized gene expression. **(B)** Violin plot showing normalized module score in each cluster, for marker gene set from previously identified reactive astrocyte cell-states. JLZ_Pan- Pan-reactive astrocytes, JLZ_A1- A1 astrocytes, JLZ_A2- A2 astrocytes from (Zamanian *et al.*, 2012), PH_Clust4- Cluster 4, PH_Clust- Cluster 8 from (Hasel *et al.*, 2021). **(C)** Violin plot showing normalized gene expression in each cluster, for homeostatic astrocyte markers (*Slc1a2*, *Glul*, *Aqp4*, *Gja1*) and reactive astrocyte markers (*Gfap*, *Vim*, *S100a6*, *Meg3*) **(D)** Dot plot showing expression of previously identified Plaque Induced Genes (PIGs) (Chen *et al.*, 2020) in each cluster. Colour scale indicates normalized expression level, scaled per gene (z-score). Dot size indicates percentage of cells, in each group, expressing the gene. **(E)** Dot plot showing expression of previously identified AD risk genes, split by experimental groups. Colour scale indicates normalized expression level, scaled per gene (z-score). Dot size indicates percentage of cells, in each group, expressing the gene. Squares around dots mark statistically significant genes (expressed in more than 25% of cells in each group and with adjusted p-value < 0.05) based on differential expression against APOE3 group. Green squares indicate genes with | Log2(Fold Change) | > 0.2. Red squares indicate

genes with $|\text{Log}_2(\text{Fold Change})| < 0.2$. **Statistical tests:** MAST differential expression test in (E), p-values were adjusted with Bonferroni correction based on the total number of genes in the dataset.

Figure S5. Apoe-deficient microglia mount reactive responses to fibrillar amyloid plaques. (A) Representation of thresholding (first step) and segmentation of microglia cell bodies, based on anti-Iba1 immunostaining, using a combination of Cellpose (second step: top panel) and Labkit (second step: bottom panel) algorithms. See Materials and Methods for details. **(B)** Representation of thresholding (first step) and tracing (second step) of primary and secondary processes of segmented microglial cell. Sum of the length of primary and secondary process calculated as “total process length”. Area of bounding box (in white) calculated as “convex area” for territory size. **(C)** Number of microglia segmented and quantified from AAV transduced cortical regions (40x magnification), at 6 months of age, from the experimental groups, further classified as plaque-associated (within X34+ thresholded plaque area and up to 5 μm outside a plaque’s edge) or non-plaque-associated. (n= 6-7 mice per group. 3 fields of view per mouse). **(D)** Bar plot showing proportion of total number of microglia from all the experimental groups (Non-plaque-associated microglia = 0.74; Plaque-associated microglia = 0.26). **(E)** Box plot showing mean distance between each microglia to its nearest three neighbours, for microglial cells classified as plaque-associated or non-plaque-associated. Data points show individual microglia from all experimental groups. **(F)** Box plots showing (i) territory size (convex area) occupied by, and (ii) total process length of, microglia classified as plaque-associated or non-plaque-associated. Data points show individual microglia from all experimental groups. Texture legends for microglia classification in (D), (E) and (F) are indicated. **(G)** IF images of AAV-APOE2 and AAV-APOE3 transduced cortical regions (see Fig. S2A) at 6 months of age. X-34 staining (white) shows the fibrillar plaque deposits. Co-staining with anti-Iba1 antibody shows microglial cells (green) and anti-Cd68 antibody shows phagocytic structures (red) inside microglia surrounding plaques. Scale bar: 100 μm . **(H)** IF images of AAV-APOE2 and AAV-APOE3 transduced cortical regions (see Fig. S2A) at 6 months of age. X-34 staining (white) shows the fibrillar plaque deposits. Co-staining with anti-Iba1 antibody shows microglia (green) and anti-CtsD antibody shows lysosomal structures (red) inside clustered microglia surrounding plaques. Scale bar: 100 μm . **(I)** Box plots showing (i) territory size (convex area) occupied by, and (ii) total process lengths of, non-plaque-associated microglial cells compared between the experimental groups. Data points show individual microglia from each experimental group. **(J)** Box plots showing (i) territory size (convex area) occupied by, and (ii) total process lengths of, plaque-associated microglial cells compared between experimental groups. Data points show individual microglia from each experimental group. Colours legends for experimental groups in (G) and (H) are indicated. **Statistical tests:** Data represented as median and interquartile range \pm values within 1.5 times the interquartile range in (D), (E), (F), (I) and (J). Linear mixed effects model in (C-E). Linear mixed effects model with Tukey’s HSD test in (F), (I) and (J). Significance shown for pairwise comparisons ****p < 0.0001

Figure S6. Astrocyte-derived APOE influences the expression of microglial cell state markers. (A) UMAP plot showing 18,569 APOE-deficient microglia (Cd11b+/Cd45-low) sorted from 6 months old mouse brains from the four experimental groups (n= 2 or 3 mice per group). Different sub-populations identified through unbiased clustering have been assigned cluster numbers. **(B)** Dot plot showing the top 10 differentially expressed genes in each cluster. Colour scale indicates normalized expression level, scaled per gene (z-score). Dot size indicates percentage of cells, in each cluster, expressing the gene. **(C)** Bar plot showing the proportion of microglia from each experimental group present in the different clusters.

Figure S7. Astrocyte-derived APOE modulates gene expression in microglia. (A) Upset plot showing number of differentially expressed genes (UP or DOWN) in microglia from each experimental group, compared to APOE3 group. Bar plot shows the number of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) common between different DE analyses (overlapping sets indicated by black dots in column below the bars). Bars are colored according to statistical significance of intersection of DEGs. **(B)** Volcano plot showing differentially expressed genes between APOEKO telencephalon astrocytes and APOE3

expressing telencephalon astrocytes. Datapoints for significant genes are coloured (Red for UP and blue for DOWN). Significance assigned based on $|\text{Log}_2(\text{Fold Change})| > 0.2$ and adjusted p-value < 0.05 . Genes discussed in text are indicated in red. **(C)** Dot plot showing expression of the 52 genes (Figure 2A) commonly upregulated in APOEKO and APOE4 microglia, split by experimental groups. Colour scale indicates normalized expression level, scaled per gene (z-score). Dot size indicates percentage of cells, in each group, expressing the gene. Plaque-induced genes (PIGs) (Chen *et al.*, 2020) are coloured in red on y-axis. **(D)** Quadrant plot comparing differential expression of genes in microglia in APOE2 vs APOE3 (along x-axis) and in APOE4 vs APOE3 (along y-axis). Colours in legend key indicate statistical significance of genes up- or downregulated in APOE2 or APOE4 or both. Significance of differentially expressed genes based on $|\text{Log}_2(\text{Fold Change})| > 0.2$ and adjusted p-value < 0.05 . Pearson's correlation, $R = 0.52$. **Statistical tests:** MAST differential expression test in (B), (C) and (D), p-values were adjusted with Bonferroni correction based on the total number of genes in the dataset.

Figure S8. APOE levels and microglia depletion. (A) Box plots showing area of Iba1+ cells (as fraction of total area in FOV) in AAV transduced cortical regions at 6 months of age, from control and PLX3397-treated (shaded) groups in (i) APOE2, (ii) APOE3, (iii) APOE4. Percentage reductions are: APOE2: 83%, APOE3: 77%, APOE4: 87%. Data points show mean value for 3 FOV per mouse ($n = 4-10$ mice per group). **(B)** Bar plots showing total APOE levels in brain homogenate from control and PLX3397-treated (shaded) groups in (i) APOE2, (ii) APOE3, (iii) APOE4, measured by MSD-ELISA. Data points show mean value for 2 technical replicates per mouse ($n = 4-10$ mice per group). **Statistical tests:** Data represented as median and interquartile range \pm values within 1.5 times the interquartile range in (A); mean \pm SEM in (B). Non-parametric Wilcoxon test in (a). Unpaired t-test in (b). * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$

Figure S9: Quality control of microglia and astrocyte single cell libraries. (A) UMAP plot showing 23,495 APOE-deficient microglia (Cd11b+/Cd45-low) sorted from 6 months old mouse brains from the four experimental groups ($n = 2$ or 3 mice per group). **(B)** Dot plot showing the top 10 differentially expressed genes in each QC cluster of microglia library. Colour scale indicates normalized expression level, scaled by gene (z-score). Dot size indicates percentage of cells, in each cluster, expressing the gene. Microglia QC Clusters 0, 1, 2, 3 and 8 have microglial identity. Contaminating cell types identified are macrophages (Microglia QC Cluster 4), endothelial cells (Microglia QC Cluster 5), mix of astrocyte and microglial cells (Microglia QC Cluster 6), monocytes (Microglia QC Clusters 7 and 9) and oligodendrocytes (QC Cluster 10). **(C)** Violin plot showing (i) nUMI (total count of RNA transcripts captured), (ii) nGene (total number of genes), (iii) mito (percentage of mitochondrial genes), (iv) ribo (percentage of ribosomal genes), in each microglial QC cluster. **(D)** UMAP plot showing 32,982 astrocytes (mCherry+/Acsa2+) sorted from 6 months old mouse brains from the four experimental groups ($n = 2$ or 3 mice per group). **(E)** Dot plot showing the top 10 differentially expressed genes in each QC cluster of astrocyte library. Colour scale indicates normalized expression level, scaled by gene (z-score). Dot size indicates percentage of cells, in each cluster, expressing the gene. Astrocyte QC Clusters 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 6 have astrocyte identity. Contaminating cell types identified are ependymal cells (Astrocyte QC Cluster 5), mural cells (Astrocyte QC Cluster 7), microglia (Astrocyte QC Cluster 9), endothelial cells (Astrocyte QC Cluster 10) and a population of undetermined identity (Astrocyte QC Cluster 8). **(F)** Violin plot showing (i) nUMI (total count of RNA transcripts captured), (ii) nGene (total number of genes), (iii) mito (percentage of mitochondrial genes), (iv) ribo (percentage of ribosomal genes), in each astrocyte QC cluster.

Table S1. List of markers identified for astrocyte clusters from single cell transcriptomic analysis.

Table S2. List of GO:Biological Process enriched terms for astrocyte clusters from functional enrichment analysis.

Table S3. List of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) (against APOE3) in astrocytes from each experimental group, with details of statistical test of overlap of DEGs between different groups.

Table S4. List of markers identified for microglia clusters from single cell transcriptomic analysis.

Table S5. List of GO:Biological Process enriched terms for microglia clusters from functional enrichment analysis.

Table S6. List of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) (against APOE3) in microglia from each experimental group, with details of statistical test of overlap of DEGs between different groups and enrichment of plaque-induced genes (PIGs) in each group.

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Figure 1

Figure 2

A

B

C

D

Figure 3

Figure 4

D

● APOEKO ● APOE2 ● APOE3 ● APOE4

▲ Total microglia

- Non-plaque-associated microglia
- Plaque-associated microglia

Figure 5

A

B

C

